

EXCELERATE Deliverable 1.2

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1. Executive Summary

The objective of EXCELERATE Deliverable 1.1 is the development of a discovery portal (bio.tools) built upon a federated curation of a registry of key software resources for bioinformatics worldwide. The core aim is to provide a practical portal that will help scientists with resource discovery and interoperability.

Four reports (D1.1 - D1.4) describe the portal:

M12 : prototyping of portal software and registry data model, addition of seed content

M24 : consolidation of software features and content to a stable model

M36 : expansion of registry content towards comprehensive coverage, with new registry features

M48 : integration with other software systems, registry applications and portal impact evaluation

This report (D1.2 at M24) describes a balance of consolidation and expansion of the prototype described in D1.1, which presented 2,550 entries as seed content. In light of these data we have validated and improved the model, ontology and software, whilst taking major strides towards comprehensive coverage of prevalent tools envisioned for D1.3.

This deliverable report describes work done with ELIXIR-EXCELERATE resources. Design and development aspects include:

production of a stable data model (biotoolsSchema 2.0.0) with improved controlled vocabularies

development of an emerging information standard for tools, based upon the model, providing a path for content quality improvement

three new EDAM ontology releases

revision of the client and server-side software including conformance to the model and new, community-requested features

Operational aspects include:

development of the community build-up process contributing to the portal (currently 537 contributors of content)

registry growth to 5,952 entries refactored to the model and with preliminary clean-up

guided by the information standard

97,262 aggregated annotations on tools including 7477 publication IDs (95% of entries)

In addition, we describe specific developments as envisioned for milestones below (all due in M24), including new prototype user interface components, features, utilities, and content developments:

M1.7.1 “Implementation of novel highly usable interfaces from analysis of user experience and usability requirements”

M1.3 “Implementation of registry-literature integration”

M1.1.2 “EDAM release with coverage of different resource categories and RIs. Implementation of tooling for sustainable community development”

M1.4 “Implementation of support for “close to source” resource annotation in key documentation generators, and software development frameworks”

Our priority to date has been tool and service providers with a focus on content growth (i.e. operating the portal and providing more content). In light of general community feedback, and specific recommendations from the EXCELERATE midterm review, focus now shifts to content quality and (somewhat longer term) an increasing priority to foster the community of tool developers and end-users. Importantly, we now have a clearer picture of the desired “endgame”: to provide a persistent reference to high-quality (curated and verified) “canonical” descriptions of unique tools, with information about their provision via online services and various downloadable artefacts, and including entries for different versions of a tool, where these have major functional differences.

Detailed information on new technical components is included. All aspects of the project are interdependent and work is ongoing in all areas, to ensure sustainable and high quality content growth, develop useful features for end-users and to support emerging integration scenarios and applications. The report describes progress made thus far and includes a summary of anticipated developments.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver a discovery portal built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key resources for bioinformatics resources world-wide	X	
2	Service monitoring, resource integration, interoperability aspects, and community centred benchmarking efforts		X
3	Deliver impact for end-users across academia, health organizations, and industry	X	

3. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

4. Adjustments made

N/A

5. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	WP1	Lead beneficiary	38 - DTU
Work package title	Tools Interoperability and Service Registry		
Start Month	1	End Month	48
Work Package Lead	Søren Brunak (DK) and Alfonso Valencia (ES)		
Objectives			
<p>WP1 will deliver a discovery portal built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key resources for bioinformatics resources world-wide. It will involve service monitoring, resource integration, interoperability aspects, and community centred benchmarking efforts. All activities, including intensive user support, are focused around delivering impact for end-users across academia, health organizations, and industry. The ELIXIR Tools and Data Services Registry is the cornerstone of the WP.</p>			
Description of work and role of partners			
<p>WP1 - Tools Interoperability and Service Registry [Months: 1-48] DTU, EMBL, UOXF, UTARTU, CNIO, CRG, IRB, INESC-ID, UiB, SIB, CNRS, IP, MU</p>			

Based on its first release in January 2015, WP1 will further develop the ELIXIR registry mechanism, interfaces and content upkeep strategy. The WP contains plans for the development and extension of its functionality and scope (Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.5). The federated curation of the registry will ensure comprehensive content and high quality annotations, both of which are essential for the sustainable impact of the registry in the community. Scientific and technical consistency and utility will be achieved by using the EDAM controlled vocabulary. Exposing the results of efforts addressing tool benchmarking and monitoring of the resources listed in the registry will provide the end-user with a robust, scientifically relevant measure of tool quality and performance. Furthermore, the work on workbench integration and interoperability will lower the cost to developers of integrating their resources in key workflow environments, and assist the users with establishing and updating their day-to-day workflows. Finally, WP1 contains plans for comprehensive, registry related user support, which will ensure impact for users, and a dynamic management element, including marketing and community development to build the federated organization behind the registry. The user-centric approach will thus stand as the guiding principle for the entire portal and guard its relevance to the community.

Task 1.1: Federated Registry Curation (96PM)

This task will deliver essential scientific and technical coverage in the registry and the vocabulary (EDAM) that underpins registry consistency and utility. A major community curation effort is required, including vocabulary development, resource annotation and registration. To ensure that the curation is high quality and sustainable, it must be federated across registry stakeholders, hence a major priority is building and supporting the community of federated curators. In tandem, the curation will be accompanied by focused software and other technical developments, that automate, validate and embed the curation process in relevant software systems; the essential underpinning of Sustainability. The registry has two primary purposes; to help discover tools and services and use them. Discovery means to find, understand, compare and select. It is a prerequisite to (inter)operability, which demands a precise understanding of software dependencies. Our approach is based on the acceptance that software interoperability will, for the foreseeable future, be implemented primarily by developers rather than intelligent software agents. We will therefore, once a comprehensive set of ELIXIR Node resources are described in basic detail, extend the curation of the registry to annotate, using EDAM Format URIs (unified resource identifiers), the data formats that are supported by tools and data services. From this, we will analyse the format-usage landscape to provide a basis for targeted software developments to improve interoperability of registered resources. We foresee these developments, which might include conversion of tools to use common formats, and development of format-converter software where needed, to be facilitated via the Matchmaking Service mechanism (D1.5).

The registry scope will be: 1. Comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including tools, data services (APIs) and host databases, prioritising ELIXIR-badged services and new resources from the Use Cases. 2. Coverage of other biomedical science Research Infrastructures (RIs), and key resources beyond ELIXIR (European and non-European). A task force will be comprised of ontology developers, curators, scientific domain experts and relevant technical experts. It will run Curation and Usability hackathons with the recurrent theme of curation: resource annotation and registration, with necessary EDAM development. To facilitate networking and community build-up, two types of social event will be combined with the hackathons: 1. Knowledge Exchange Workshops, including representatives of relevant infrastructures, institutes and projects, on themes related to the registry suggested by the community. 2. Cross-domain

Strategy Workshops to gather technical officers from ELIXIR Nodes, RIs, key resources, and other key initiatives, to discuss and develop common approaches for registry curation across RIs internationally. EDAM provides the registry with a consistent vocabulary for topics (general

scientific and technical disciplines), operations (tool functions), types of data, and specific data formats and data identifiers. Task 1.1 will work with the existing EDAM community, develop its open governance and contribution mechanisms and deliver essential utilities to ensure that maintenance, validation and community development is sustainable in the long term. We will assess and validate coverage by correlating EDAM concepts to terms used for curation, which will then inform and drive necessary additions and desirable clean-ups (removal of concepts). We will develop focused essential utilities for EDAM maintenance including automation of the release process, basic validation of content, reporting of changes between versions, deployment to ontology browsers such as BioPortal and OLS, technical integration of EDAM with applications including the registry and others, mapping of provider-supplied terms and phrases to EDAM, and revise annotation upon new EDAM releases. To underpin the sustainability of the federated curation, this task will deliver focused software and other technical developments that will automate the registration and update of provider-supplied information, leveraging their own local software infrastructure where possible. We will work with providers to support them in doing this, and, where possible, adapt technically the local solutions to make them more broadly applicable to others. Further, in order to facilitate coverage, all relevant resource providers will be given smooth and convenient access to resource registration. This will be achieved by a combination of simple-to-obtain local login accounts and opening for using eduGAIN authentication to register resources. Finally, this task will ensure that registered resource are citable, discoverable by the major search engines, and are placed in scientific context. It will also include technical mark-up to support “Semantic Web” applications, e.g. Schema.org compatible microdata or RDFa to support Google “rich snippets” and other structured search results in the major browsers. Hence, the registry will promote the registered resources and deliver impact for developers and institutes by making resources rank higher in search results and hence more findable.

Task 1.1 partners: DK, NO, FR, CH, CZ, EMBL-EBI, PT

Task 1.2: Benchmarking and Monitoring (15PM)

This task will support the monitoring and community benchmarking of analytical tools, in a systematic and sustainable way e.g. based on the efforts in WP2. Firstly, it will review the existing service quality and performance metrics and assess their usefulness in the context of a registry. This may require development of a light-weight controlled vocabulary capturing the concepts distilled from the preparatory activities above and those of WP2.

Task 1.2 partners: DK, ES, CZ, CH

Task 1.3: Workbench integration and interoperability (36PM)

There is general trend towards the use of workflows as a preferred environment for the convenient use of tools and data access, especially when resources must be used in combination with one another. This task will boost convenience and resource interoperability by implementing a Workbench Integration Enabler service that will develop the vision “register your software once - get it supported everywhere”. Technically, this service will translate the description of any tool or service that is registered in the Tools and Data Services Registry into the metadata format required by the existing major workbenches, including Mobylye, Galaxy and Taverna. Furthermore, we will develop a new, lightweight Service Launchpad for running tools and services which have programmatic access and which can be invoked using information available in the registry. To develop the Enabler Service, we will align the registry software description model and the schemas used by the workbench systems or required by the Launchpad, and subsequently revise the model and schemas to facilitate the metadata transfer. Furthermore, to prove the principle, new high priority tools and services, including those developed in the Use Cases.

Task 1.3 partners: DK, EE, FR, CH, PT

Task 1.4: User support and derived registry development (36.7PM)

This task will provide direct and indirect user support to deliver impact for ELIXIR end-users. Direct support will be achieved primarily by leveraging the existing and highly popular user bioinformatics forums (BioStars, BioPlanet etc.).

A User-support specialist will patrol such forums and respond to questions in one of four ways: 1) Where resources answering to the Users needs exist in the registry, a link to them in the registry will be provided via our API. 2) Where resources exist in the registry, but the registry API cannot be used to answer the question directly, they will request new features of the API and in so doing drive development of the Query Interface. 3) Where an appropriate resource exists but has not been registered, they will request the appropriate registry curator add it to the registry. 4) Where a registered resource exists that is close, but not quite what is required, they will forward feature requests to the appropriate developers, possibly via the Matchmaking Service (D1.5).

Indirect user support will be achieved primarily by ensuring the registry interfaces are highly usable and match very closely the needs of the user. To achieve this, we will run user experience sessions during the Curation and Usability community. Scientific and technical consistency and utility will be achieved by using the EDAM controlled vocabulary.

Exposing the results of efforts addressing tool benchmarking and monitoring of the resources listed in the registry will provide the end-user with a robust, scientifically relevant measure of tool quality and performance. Furthermore, the hackathons (see Task 1.1) in order to evaluate usability. We will develop comprehensive Good Practice Guidelines for the curation of the registry in all aspects, but in particular the annotation of common types of resources using EDAM.

We will also participate in the development of an ELIXIR Experts Registry where users can discover relevant expertise within the ELIXIR network, and an ELIXIR User Helpdesk to answer general questions concerning use of the registry, forwarding specialised scientific and technical enquiries to relevant experts.

Task 1.4 partners: DK, CH

Task 1.5: Management, marketing and community build-up (46PM)

This task will build the federated organisation primarily by identifying and facilitating key collaborations between registry stakeholders. This will be achieved by organising 'Resource Synergy Meetings', where we will identify and encourage targeted software developments, e.g. to coordinate curation and data sharing. We will also promote resource integration and usability, e.g. by cross-linking resources and through API harmonization. As a prerequisite to these Synergy Meetings, a Resource Metadata Catalogue, listing all relevant resources, their scientific and technical scope, and information fields (schema), will be compiled and used to compare providers and identify redundancies. We will also use these meeting to cross-link the Tools & Data Services Registry with other key ELIXIR registries, for example the Training Materials Registry, the ELIXIR Events Registry, and the Experts Registry.

This task will also develop an oversight and management strategy and leverage partners within and beyond the ELIXIR organisation to implement strategy. To drive delivery, it will identify and encourage collaboration, monitor actions, identify delays, and intervene where necessary. It will raise community awareness and therefore impact by contributing to a forceful marketing campaign via all appropriate marketing channels, including popular social media. It will provide support to

fundlers, publishers and others at the EU and national level, that policy is aligned with the aims of the registry organisation.

Task 1.5 partners: DK

Partner number, short name and effort: 1 - EMBL 12.00; 2 - UOXF 6.00; 5 - UTARTU 43.00; 7 - CNIO 2.00; 8 - CRG 11.00; 10 - IRB 8.00; 17 - INESC-ID 4.00; 21 - UiB 18.00; 25 - SIB 9.50; 26 - CNRS 9.00; 29 - IP 12.00; 35 - MU 18.20; 38 - DTU 76.00

6. REPORT: Registry release with comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including resource data format curation and analysis

6.1 Technical Overview

We have further developed the core technical components of the portal:

- **software description model** (Section 6.3). The first stable version (biotoolsSchema 2.0.0) was developed and moved to production. The registration interface, query interface, back-end architecture, and API were all refactored, and the registry content (Section 6.5) migrated for compliance. This work is proceeding in three phases, the first of which is complete (see Appendix B & H9).
- **EDAM ontology** (Section 6.3.3). Three versions (1.16 - 1.18) were released, alongside improved continuous integration process and tooling.
- **controlled vocabularies** (Section 6.3.4). The 9 vocabularies described in D1.1 were refactored and extended into 16 specialised vocabularies.
- **registration interface** (Section 6.6.1). Various usability improvements were made.
- **query interface** (Section 6.6.2). Various improvements were made to the search bar, summary view, grid view and Tool Cards.
- **back-end architecture** (Section 6.6.4). Better administrator tooling, improved user account management, and better performing search functionality optimised in light of end-user critique.
- **tool IDs and persistent URLs** (Section 6.6.4.4). The scheme has been simplified.
- **API** (Section 6.6.4.5). Support for bio.tools subdomains added.

New core technical components were developed:

- **entry management** (Section 6.6.3) including a new content ownership and edit permissions model, subdomain management and new end-user **MyProfile pages**.
- **Project metrics** (Section 6.6.5). Various new content and project metrics were implemented as part of a broader system for automated housekeeping tasks.

Current work in progress:

- **tool information standard** (Section 6.4, Appendix C). An emerging information standard for tools based upon biotoolsSchema, providing a path for content quality improvement.
- **QC/QA architecture** (Section 6.6.4.7) for quality control and assurance, including QC checks with issues reporting. This is based on the emerging Curation Guidelines and will power a curator interface for validating bio.tools entries as per the information standard.

Specific developments contributing to the milestones M1.1.2, M1.3, M1.4 and M1.7.1 are described below.

The portal content and most of the technical components (excluding the portal software itself) are available under open license (Appendix K).

6.1.1 Milestone M1.7.1 (novel user interfaces)

M1.7.1 (“Implementation of novel highly usable interfaces from analysis of user experience and usability requirements”) as envisioned in the EXCELERATE proposal would boost bio.tools usability through appropriate user interface (UI) developments. We have developed mock-ups and working prototypes for a completely revised bio.tools user interface and for other novel UI components designed to improve overall usability of the site, and the experience of users when registering, editing, searching for or browsing bio.tools entries. The work is based upon intensive user critique harvested mostly during events described in D1.1 and in Appendix A.1.

Mock-ups (on paper) with partial implementation:

- **bio.tools landing page** redesign (Appendix G.1)
- **topics view** (Appendix G.4) for scientific topic-based navigation based on the EDAM ontology
- **curators interface** (Appendix G.7) for validating bio.tools entries (mock-up only) as per the emerging information standard

Prototypes (in code):

- **Tool Cards** (Appendix G.2) with fresh new look
- **summary view** (Appendix G.3) with fresh new look tool “mini-cards”
- **grid view** (Appendix G.5) redesign: more powerful, compact and clean
- **tool annotator** (Appendix G.6) for greatly improved tool registration (prototype based on mockup from M1.1.1)
- **biotoolsSum (collections view)** (biotoolsSum, Appendix G.8) UI providing an overview of tool collections, for use on external Web sites

6.1.2 Milestone M1.1.2 (EDAM + tooling)

M1.1.2 (“EDAM release with coverage of different resource categories and RIs. Implementation of tooling for sustainable community development”). We have developed EDAM content and new utilities for its development and exploitation.

- **EDAM ontology** with continuous integration (see above)

- **EDAM Formats sub-ontology curation:** completed plans for a comprehensive catalogue of data formats (Section 6.3.3.2, Appendix D)
- **edamMap utility** for mapping text to EDAM terms, as applied to bio.tools content imports *en masse* (in production, Appendix J.1)
- **tool annotator** prototype (see above)

6.1.3 Milestone M1.3 (registry-literature integration)

M1.3 (“Implementation of registry-literature integration”) as envisioned in the EXCELERATE proposal would ensure software is more citable and placed in scientific context. We summarise various developments of the bio.tools software and content, and future plans, to advance these goals and better integrate bio.tools with the scientific literature.

- Software developments to expose literature data in bio.tools (Section 6.6.2.5):
 - Use of the AltMetric bookmarklet
- A systematic approach to the annotation of tool publications, resulting in 95% of all 6800+ entries now having at least one publication ID (Section 6.5.2.2)
- Systematic creation of unique tool identifiers based on standardised, URL-safe version of supplied tool names, used in Tool Card URLs to provide a persistent reference to “canonical” tool descriptions (*in progress*) (Section 6.5.4.2)
- Plans for future deeper literature integration (Appendix H.11) including additional software developments:
 - Rendering basic information for tool publications, in copy-pastable form
 - Inclusion of citation counts
 - Sorting bio.tools entries by citation count and AltMetric attention score

6.1.4 Milestone M1.4 (“close to source” annotation)

M1.4 (“Implementation of support for “close to source” resource annotation in key documentation generators, and software development frameworks”) as envisioned in the EXCELERATE proposal would implement developments to embed bio.tools-compatible tool annotation in upstream systems, *i.e.* closer to the tool source code, developer or maintainer of existing tool metadata, leveraging existing systems and in so doing put the entire bio.tools distributed distribution curation effort on a more sustainable footing.

We scoped in detail various options to the ends above; this is a broad ranging and hard problem, with many possibilities but with numerous complex technical dependencies and challenges. With limited resources for this task we focussed on three high priority areas, taking decisive steps towards realising the vision above.

- Development, testing and application of a tool to **import database API metadata** via the openAPI specification into bio.tools: a critical development to expose data services in bio.tools in a sustainable way (Sections 3.5.5 & Appendix J.2)
- A publication of ReGaTE (Registration of Galaxy Tools in Elixir), a software utility that automates the process of **registering services in a Galaxy instance** within bio.tools: a critical development to ensure this information can be gathered in a sustainable way.

This is described in D1.6 report¹ and was applied to the Galaxy instance at Institut Pasteur (Appendix E.9).

Doppelt-Azeroual, O., Mareuil, F., Deveaud, Kalaš, M., Soranzo, N., van den Beek, M., Grüning, B., Ison, J. and Ménager, H. (2017) GigaScience, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/gix022>

- A generic technical **strategy for integration of bio.tools with other resources**, in a way that supports these resources, underpins the sustainable growth of bio.tools and helps to establish bio.tools as the primary archive of basic tool metadata for unique tools (Appendix I)

6.2 Community build-up process

The agile, community-driven, user-centered approach first described in D1.1 continues to be applied to all aspects of the project. The result is clarification of the scope of the registry (Section 6.2.1), aims and target audience (Section 6.2.2), and strides forward in the technical implementation (Sections 3.3 - 3.6). Community build-up has continued, resulting in a growing and active community who are helping drive development forward. It has, however, been necessary to balance outreach activities with core developments of the content (Section 6.5) and software (Section 6.6), and this trend will continue in the next reporting period, in particular, with more focussed developments to engage developers (Appendix H.4 & H.5) and support end-users (Appendix H.12).

Events. WP1 personnel participated in a total of 13 events (Appendix A.1), including hackathons of the types described in D1.1, in order to develop or promote the portal.

Open governance models described in D1.1 have been revised to encourage participation:

- the bio.tools governance is now better documented². The ‘registry-core’ group has grown from 29 (in D1.1) to 37 members.
- the EDAM governance model is now better documented³ and has been streamlined to make it much more open to participation
 - The ‘edam-core’ developers group has been replaced with an ‘edam-dev’ group with open participation and mailing lists
 - The Steering and Advisory groups have been consolidated into a single Steering Group, with more focus on (and open to) adopters of EDAM
 - A nominated release manager (Hervé Ménager currently) is responsible for ensuring regular EDAM releases

To improve governance further still, we will:

- consolidate EDAM Editors⁴ with bio.tools Thematic Editors⁵ (Section 6.2.3.2, Appendix A.2) *i.e.* constitute a single group of people with responsibility for oversight of scientific areas in bio.tools and EDAM.
- invite known adopters of EDAM to join the Steering Group

¹ <http://tinyurl.com/WP1-D1-6>

² <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/governance.html>

³ <http://edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/governance.html>

⁴ <http://edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributors.html#edam-editors>

⁵ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributors.html#registry-core-registry-editors>

Sifterapp⁶ has proven highly efficient for high-level task management and technical coordination. Membership⁷ has increased to 111 members.

- 382 issues tracked (250 open, 132 closed).

GitHub organisations for bio.tools⁸ (23 members) and EDAM⁹ (12 members) remain the preferred method for public discussion and tracking fine-grained issues

- 229 bio.tools issues¹⁰ tracked (144 open, 85 closed)
- 85 biotoolsSchema issues¹¹ tracked (27 open, 58 closed)
- 312 EDAM issues tracked¹² (101 open, 211 closed)

JIRA remains in use for tracking low-level (implementation) software tasks and has been opened to WP1 partners.

Community mailing lists¹³ remain low-traffic with discussion encouraged on sifterapp instead. The registry-support list (for questions and help on bio.tools) is seeing increased traffic and typically gets a same day response.

Monthly hangouts for bio.tools¹⁴ and now also for EDAM¹⁵ with open agenda and attendance continue to provide a useful forum for general discussions.

Weekly hangouts for the Curation Taskforce (Section 6.2.3.1) were started recently and provide an effective means to coordinate the core curation tasks.

6.2.1 Scope of the registry

A major clarification of scope was made, based upon the vision of bio.tools becoming a sustainable primary archive for basic tool metadata, providing a persistent reference to high-quality (curated and verified) “canonical” descriptions of *unique* tools, with information about their provision *via* online services and various downloadable artefacts, and including entries for different versions of a tool, where these have major functional differences. The technical scope (types of application software) remains as described in D1.1.

6.2.2 Aims, target audience and use-cases

The aims, target audience and uses-cases described in D1.1 remain, however, in light of specific feedback from the EXCELERATE midterm review additional priorities are apparent:

- *Full engagement with other EXCELERATE Work Packages should be put in focus.* Practical steps will include assignment of Thematic Editors (Section 6.2.3.2.) for applicable work packages and exposing metrics for data resources from WP3. Crucially, integration with WP2 will be the subject of deliverable D1.5.

⁶ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com>

⁷ This was erroneously reported in D1.1 as having 132 members

⁸ <https://github.com/bio-tools/>

⁹ <https://github.com/edamontology/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsregistry/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsschema>

¹² <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology>

¹³ http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributors_guide.html#mailing-list

¹⁴ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/hangouts.html>

¹⁵ <http://edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/hangouts.html>

- *Strong recommendation to focus on partnership with developers, and create a Europe-wide community of developers.*
 This is a hard, multifaceted problem, but can be achieved partly through traditional outreach actions, and through technical developments that were partly envisioned in M1.6 (resource metadata catalogue) but will need to be greatly enhanced (see Appendix H.4 & H.5).
- *There are scalability challenges and a need to engage with end-users and developers: T1.4 (end user support via popular forums) and T1.5 (thematic editors) are excellent ideas to this end.*
 End-user support (Appendix H.12) will be the subject of D1.7 and - with thematic editors (Section 6.2.3.2, Appendix A.2) - will be given higher priority.

The priority to date has been *tool providers*, especially major institutional providers and other collections that provide bio.tools entries. Priorities must shift more towards *tool developers* and ultimately be squarely focussed on *tool users*, supporting them with discovery and interoperability of tools.

6.2.3 Distributed community curation

There are 537 unique contributors (people with bio.tools user accounts) of content to the registry. The contributor growth (Fig. 1) was rapid from 2015 Q2 to 2016 Q2 thanks to a major programme of events¹⁶, and since then has been linear. This organic (*i.e.* unsolicited) growth is encouraging and shows there is a natural pull of new content to the registry.

Figure 1. Contributor growth. The blue line is the total number of contributors, grey line is new contributors that month.

The distribution of contributors by top-level domain (Fig. 2) shows that email addresses in “.com” (commercial) is the primary domain, followed by France, Germany, Denmark, United Kingdom and then “.edu” (United States-affiliated institutions of higher education).

¹⁶ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/events.html>

Figure 2. Contributors by top-level domain

Achieving high quality content given the highly complex, distributed and dynamic software landscape remains a very hard problem. To mitigate these difficulties:

- Direct assistance with curation, and particularly EDAM annotation including the creation of new terms has continued *via* mailing lists, sifterapp and GitHub (Section 6.2)
- Actions of the curation task-force (Section 6.2.3.1)
- An emerging group of thematic editors for bio.tools and EDAM (Section 6.2.3.2, Appendix A.2)
- Coordination of a new studentship scheme to support students to contribute (Section 6.2.3.3)

A priority will be establishing stable mechanisms for synchronisation of content, where necessary, with major tool providers (see Appendix I).

6.2.3.1 Curation Taskforce

A curation taskforce, the core of which is staff from the Danish, Estonian and Czech nodes, now meets weekly to coordinate curation tasks. They have joined scientific domain experts and ontologists at various events (Section A.1) in response to acute needs to assist partners. The taskforce's primary mission is to drive high quality content growth towards comprehensive coverage of the prevalent bioinformatics tools. We anticipate they will take a major role in supporting the emerging Thematic Editors (see below).

6.2.3.2 Thematic Editors

Thematic editors are registry-core¹⁷ members responsible for overseeing coverage and quality in specific thematic areas. The editorships will enable expanding accurate high-standard software annotations in bio.tools to most scientific topics in life science. We have currently nine nominated thematic editors, however the concept is still in the early stages; we summarise our progress thus far Appendix A.2.

6.2.3.3 bio.tools studentship scheme

ELIXIR Denmark - the coordinating node of the bio.tools project - is supporting studentships to work on curation-focussed mini-projects for bio.tools. Projects must have clear and quantifiable impact on bio.tools content, in terms of number of entries and / or content quality. Full documentation for the schema is available¹⁸. The process by which projects are proposed and approved is open and mostly managed in sifterapp¹⁹. Finalised proposals are uploaded to GitHub²⁰. The scheme is proving an efficient means to improve the registry, achieve outreach and support key partners. Active projects include:

- “Mining the Scientific Literature for and Annotating Proteomics Software using the EDAM ontology and biotoolsSchema”²¹
- “Harvesting service descriptions for bio.tools using OpenAPI standards”²²
- “Annotating software tools in a scientific context”²³
- “Annotating software tools in domains of the Life Sciences”²⁴

6.2.4 Documentation

Great efforts are being made to comprehensively and professionally document all aspects of the project and its products. The following documentation will be described in detail (once more mature) in a future deliverable report:

- **bio.tools docs** including Contributor Guide, User Guide, Editor Guide, API reference, studentship scheme and governance. Noteworthy is the emerging **Curators Guide** that will provide general, attribute-specific and tool-type specific guidelines for the curation of bio.tools, including quality control checks that will be used to verify entry quality (Section G.7):
<https://biotools.readthedocs.io/>
- **biotoolsSchema docs** including comprehensive technical documentation encoded within schema and available online:
<https://biotoolsschema.readthedocs.io/>
<https://bio.tools/schema>
- **EDAM ontology docs** including basic details, technical details, Users Guide, Contributors Guide, Editors Guide and governance:
<https://edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁷ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/governance.html#registry-core>

¹⁸ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/studentships.html>

¹⁹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com>

²⁰ <https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/>

²¹ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/proteomics_software.pdf

²² <https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/openAPI.pdf>

²³ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/literature_integration.pdf

²⁴ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/thematic_editing.pdf

6.3 Software description model

Three revisions of the candidate stable software description model (biotoolsXSD 2.0 beta01) described in D1.1 were made, in light of intensive community critique, to produce the first stable version (biotoolsSchema 2.0.0), which defines the scope and potential functionality of bio.tools for years to come. Software attributes were prioritised with implementation proceeding in 3 phases. We have completed phase 1, which prioritises those attributes for which most data is available. This a major development. Phases 2 and 3 will be rolled out in due course (Appendix H.9). The model will be subject to future improvements, but breaking changes are now restricted to once per year to provide stability for the bio.tools developers and external developers and dependencies.

6.3.1 Software attributes

Highlights of the improvements made over the candidate stable schema (described in D1.1) in the production of biotoolsSchema 2.0.0 are summarised in Appendix B.1.

6.3.2 Model of tool function

While the basic model of tool function described in D1.1 remains sound, the need for better guidelines for annotating a tool's functionality has become apparent. Specific guidelines are being developed as part of the emerging Curators Guide (Section 6.2.4). There is also scope to improve the model making it less ambiguous (Appendix H.10).

6.3.3 EDAM ontology

EDAM development remains use-case driven, primarily by bio.tools but also now by Galaxy, where it has potential to provide a common vocabulary with bio.tools and provide users with additional information for tool discovery and workflow composition.

All EDAM versions are available for download²⁵ and browsing from BioPortal²⁶ or EMBL-EBI OLS²⁷. Highlights of changes follow; see the online summary of changes²⁸ and detailed changelog²⁹ for exact details of changes. Four new releases were made:

- **EDAM_1.16:** updates and additions for text mining, natural language processing (BioNLP), gene expression *etc.* Structural improvements and fixes, improvements of synonyms, and new attributes for Formats
- **EDAM_1.17:** new concepts for describing sequencing / analysis tools (from SEQWiki), deprecation of multiple Topics to improve simplicity and usability, new attributes for better provenance on deprecated concepts
- **EDAM_1.18:** refactoring including Operation concept deprecations to make this branch simpler and improve usability, new attribute to provide tips (*e.g.* in bio.tools UI) for curators, indicating "organisational classes" (concepts not normally recommended for annotation).

²⁵ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology>

²⁶ <http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/EDAM>

²⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/edam>

²⁸ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/blob/master/changelog.md>

²⁹ <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/blob/master/changelog-detailed.md>

6.3.3.1 EDAM continuous integration

Following a barebones implementation mentioned in M1.1.1, we have developed the **EDAM Continuous Integration (CI)**; an automatic control that checks the EDAM ontology at every modification for a number of potential errors using:

- **edamxpathvalidator** (<https://github.com/edamontology/edamxpathvalidator>) checks a number of consistency rules and best practices in the EDAM ontology, including numerical IDs consistency and unicity across different axes, unlinking of deprecated terms, terms labelling style, synonyms consistency.
- The **Hermit reasoner** (<http://www.hermit-reasoner.com>) to apply more general rules of internal consistency in the ontology.

This CI process has eliminated the need for many tedious manual controls, and will enable a more frequent pace for the releases of EDAM.

6.3.3.2 EDAM Formats sub-ontology

EDAM aspires to provide a comprehensive and practical catalogue of data formats used in the life sciences, as this can support applications in tool interoperability and workflow composition. To this end, we have concluded planning (Appendix D) in addition to adding miscellaneous new formats in the reporting period.

6.3.4 Controlled vocabularies

The nine controlled vocabularies described in D1.1 were refactored and extended to increase usability and specificity, yielding a total of 16 controlled vocabularies (Appendix B.2) in the stable schema. Notably the **license** controlled vocabulary was refactored to use identifiers from the industry standard SPDX license list³⁰. Comprehensive documentation including definitions of each term in applicable vocabularies is available online³¹ and in the XSD file itself³².

6.4 Tool information standard

biotoolsSchema (with EDAM) provide a rigorous and consistent specification of the syntax and semantics for tool metadata. What it cannot in itself provide, but which are now apparent as sorely needed are:

- accessible summary of what type of information bio.tools provides
- flexible information requirement, including a minimum requirement presenting a low barrier to new registrations, compatible / enabling integration with other major related cataloguing efforts (*e.g.* BioContainers³³)
- quality tiers to motivate individual entry owners to improve their entries (curation as a "game"), with a "gold standard" of entry quality for curators to aspire to
- a framework / workflow to guide tasks and priorities of curators, thematic editors (Section 6.2.3.2, Appendix A.2) and bio.tools admin

³⁰ <https://spdx.org/licenses/>

³¹ <https://bio.tools/schema>

³² <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsSchema/blob/master/versions/biotools-2.0.0/biotools-2.0.0.xsd>

³³ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

- a basis for metrics of bio.tools quality, KPIs (key performance indicators) of quality improvement objectives, and targets
- a component of branding bio.tools as a trusted source of quality tool information

All of these things can be achieved through adoption by bio.tools of a standard for tool information. Following multiple iterations driven by community input³⁴, we have an emerging candidate information standard for description of tools.

The standard is based on biotoolsSchema, but goes beyond the syntactic / semantic constraints that can be defined in a XML schema. It has two parts:

- a list of *what* tool attributes must be specified, or stated as not being available, at various tiers of entry *completeness*
- a set of Curation Guidelines describing *how* each attribute should be specified, to provide annotation *quality*

The recent EXCELERATE midterm review recommended “*devotion of effort to ensure that inclusion of tools in the catalogue is perceived as an important label of quality and value*”. The standard underpins labelling of entries based on entry completeness and quality, with a possibility to label other facets of “quality” and “value” of tools and data resources in due course (Appendix H.8).

The standard (Appendix C) including the Curation Guidelines (Section 6.2.4) will be described in detail D1.3.

6.5 Portal content

6.5.1 Content summary

As of July 2017, the registry includes a total of 5952 entries. Content growth (Fig. 3) rose very sharply from 2016 Q3 to 2017 Q4 as imports *en masse* providing coverage of major collections (Section 6.5.3, Appendix E) were completed, and then until 2017 Q2 was linear. The levelling off and then drop in the number of entries from May 2017 is owing to progress in entry de-duplication (Section 6.5.4.1)

We are confident the registry contains a representative subset of all tools and is approaching a reasonable coverage of all the major prevalent tools that must, in due course, be included. Much of content growth was a result of imports *en masse* providing coverage of key collections (Section 6.5.3, Appendix E). The remainder has come from unsolicited contributions, *i.e.* organic growth.

³⁴ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsSchema/issues/77>

Figure 3. Content growth. Number of bio.tools entries vs. time.

6.5.2 Content annotation

Content is annotated as per attributes defined within biotoolsSchema (Section 6.3) including in terms from the EDAM ontology (Section 6.3.3) and other controlled vocabularies (Section 6.3.4, Appendix B.2). The registry now includes a total of 97,262 individual annotations.

Note: Annotations are calculated according to the emerging information standard (Section 6.4, Appendix C), where attributes are grouped for purposes of determining adherence to the standard. For example, a single annotation for "Documentation" group implies that one of "General documentation", "API documentation" or "API specification" attributes were specified.

The graph of number of annotations over time (Fig. 4) follows a similar pattern (and explanation) to content growth (Fig. 3).

Figure 4. Annotation growth. Number of annotations on bio.tools entries versus time.

A breakdown of the annotations by type (Table 1) reveals that the priorities have been EDAM Topic and Operation annotations (Section 6.5.2.1) and publications (Section 6.5.2.2).

Annotation type	Number of entries
Name	5952
Description	5952
Homepage	5952
Tool Type	7297
Unique ID	5952
Topic	14397
Publication	7477
Contact	4246
Operation	14466
Documentation	2933
Operating System	2056
Input Output	6724
Code availability	5014
Accessibility	393
Data format	5112
Community	1436
Downloads	1903
Total	97262

Table 1. Annotations by type. The number of aggregated metrics of each type defined in the emerging tool information standard is shown.

6.5.2.1 EDAM annotations

The registry includes a total of 40,699 individual EDAM annotations. The large spike in the number of annotations (Fig. 5, Fig. 6) corresponds to the *en masse* content imports (Section 6.5.3, Appendix E) and the subsequent drop in overall annotations, and most pronouncedly for the EDAM Data and Format annotations is owing to a post-import clean-up (Section 6.5.4); many tools were registered with default (top-level) EDAM annotations and these have been subsequently removed.

Figure 5. EDAM annotation growth. Total number of EDAM Topic, Operation, Data or Format annotations versus time.

Figure 6. EDAM annotation growth (breakdown). Total number of EDAM Topic (grey line), Operation (red), Data (blue) and Format (cyan) annotations versus time.

6.5.2.2 Systematic annotation of tool publications

Annotating bio.tools entries with publication information provides advantages to both bio.tools users and tool providers. The user can inspect the resource publication and gathers a better understanding of the scientific and technical context, whilst the provider may gain better exposure and thus higher citation of their publication. biotoolsSchema³⁵ thus bio.tools supports specification of tool publications as one or more DOI (Digital Object Identifier), PMID (PubMed reference number) and PMCID (PubMed Central reference number).

As part of a broader drive to improve overall bio.tools content quality, systematic annotation of publication IDs was performed. The goal was to annotate all entries with publication information where possible, and to identify tools with no associated publication and mark them accordingly. This involved:

- developments³⁶ such that tools may be annotated as being without a publication; *i.e.* a publication could not be found at a certain date, rather than the entry merely lacking a publication ID
- programmatic collection of IDs (from analysis of bio.tools homepage, name and documentation URL) with manual verification
- manual collection of IDs (where necessary)

The result (Table 2) is near comprehensive annotation of publication IDs for bio.tools entries.

bio.tools entries	5852
#publication annotations	7477

³⁵ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsschema>

³⁶ This feature is supported in the bio.tools back-end but not currently by biotoolsSchema or bio.tools UI.

Tools with at least 1 publication	5627 (96.1% coverage) 3525 PMIDs 146 PMCIDs 3857 DOIs
Tools marked as without a publication	225 (3.9%)

Table 2. Results of systematic annotation of publication IDs.

6.5.3 Coverage of collections

Coverage of various major tool collections (Table 3) has been accomplished or is in progress: see Appendix E for details.

Collection	Description
BioConductor https://www.bioconductor.org/	R packages for the analysis and comprehension of high-throughput genomic data.
Bioinformatics Links Directory https://bioinformatics.ca/links_directory/	Curated links to molecular resources, tools and databases.
NAR Web Servers and Database Issues https://bioinformatics.ca/links_directory/journals/nar	Tools and databases published by Nucleic Acids Research (NAR) journal.
SEQwiki https://www.semantic-mediawiki.org/wiki/SEQwiki	Next generation sequencing and genomics tools.
ExpASY http://www.expasy.org/	Databases and tools in different areas of life sciences from the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics.
msutils.org http://www.ms-utils.org/wiki/pmwiki.php/Main/SoftwareList	Free (gratis) software for analysis of mass spectrometry data.
Tools used by trainers	Popular tools used by ELIXIR training community.
GO tools	Tools used by the Gene Ontology (GO) consortium.
Institut Pasteur Galaxy services	Diverse bioinformatics services maintained in the Galaxy server from Institut Pasteur.
de.NBI tools and services	Tools and services from the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI).

Table 3. Tool collections covered by bio.tools.

6.5.4 Content review & clean-up

During the prototyping phase (D1.1) and the current reporting period, the priority was rapid content expansion. Whilst major content growth was achieved (Section 6.5.1), an undesirable consequence was the inclusion of some low or variable quality entries, including duplicate entries with redundant or inconsistent information. With the desired “endgame” (Section 1) in mind, a review of the content was conducted^{37,38}. The output of this review includes specific QC checks (Section 6.6.4.7) as enumerated in the emerging Curation Guidelines (Section 6.2.4), and a major refactoring and clean-up of the content that is currently in progress:

- Consolidation of duplicate entries (Section 6.5.4.1)
- Refactoring for clean tool names and identifiers (Section 6.5.4.2)
- Refactoring entries to describe unique tools³⁹
- Assignment of entry ownership⁴⁰
- Improving EDAM Topic & Operation annotations⁴¹

6.5.4.1 Entry de-duplication

Duplicate entries, *i.e.* describing (possibly different facets of) the same tool arise because of:

- independent registration of the same tool by different users
- parallel imports of tools en-masse, *e.g.* from other tool collections or curation hackathons, aiming for rapid coverage
- independent registration of different implementations or interfaces of the same tool, *e.g.* an online service providing the functions of a command-line tool

Duplicates are a source of redundancy and inconsistency that compromise the portal’s discovery function, *e.g.* multiple search results for the same tool may confuse users. On the other hand, duplicate entries often contain useful complementary information. Thus, consolidation of duplicates is a high priority and we’re taking a systematic approach:

1. automatically identify potential duplicates for all entries by comparison of tool names and homepage URLs (not 100% reliable)
2. manual inspection to confirm duplicates⁴² and hide these from view
3. consolidate duplicates by merging annotations and re-publication of a single, canonical tool description

This work is ongoing⁴³. Duplicates are not entirely avoidable, thus, we will complete the entry-deduplication described and then implemented a more sustainable approach:

- guidelines (Section 6.2.4), including within the bio.tools user interface, for users to check the registry and take appropriate action, before registering a tool

³⁷ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/229>

³⁸ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/195>

³⁹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/40>

⁴⁰ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/171>

⁴¹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/156>

⁴² see

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11sF19YUMEjFrMLEoaT7eJg-kH0UCyCr7iv5C_n53ZiM/edit?usp=drive_web

⁴³

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11sF19YUMEjFrMLEoaT7eJg-kH0UCyCr7iv5C_n53ZiM/edit?usp=drive_web

- duplicate detection and reporting mechanism, ideally preventing duplicates in the first place
- consolidation of duplicates upon detection, as part of routine housekeeping

6.5.4.2 Refactoring tool names & identifiers

There are practical difficulties in providing “cool URIs” (Section 6.6.4.4) required by the portal:

- duplicate entries with the same or similar tool names
- tools with very long names that are not readily transformable to a usable identifier
- misappropriation of original tool names, especially entries for online services over those tools

Action to address this includes:

- guidelines for tool names⁴⁴, and their consistent transformation to toolIDs, as part of a broader set of Curation Guidelines (Section 6.2.4)
- systematic refactoring of existing tool names (and thus IDs) conforming to standards above is in progress⁴⁵
- systematic creation of entries for tools currently described by an entry for some online service only

6.5.5 Import of data service API metadata via OpenAPI

The OpenAPI⁴⁶ specification, previously called Swagger, is a description format for REST⁴⁷ and REST-like API services that is vendor neutral, portable and open. OpenAPI shares with bio.tools the common goal of providing users with better API descriptions, thus, being able to interconvert specifications has potential for the efficient re-use and sharing of metadata. ELIXIR-DK and Maastricht University ran an bio.tools studentship (Section 6.2.3.3) focused on converting OpenAPI 2.0 documentation files into bio.tools format. The OpenAPI-Importer utility (Appendix J.2) was developed for this purpose, and applied resulting in the registration of 9 APIs over biological databases (Table 4).

This is work in progress, with potential for providing in a sustainable way rich descriptions of data services, and will be described in more details in D1.3.

Database	bio.tools entry
Ensembl	https://bio.tools/tool/Ensembl_OpenAPI2Biotools/version/none
OSDB	https://bio.tools/tool/OSDB_API/version/none
Open TG-GATEs API	https://bio.tools/tool/Open_TG-GATEs_API/version/none
ORCID	https://bio.tools/tool/Orcid_API/version/none

⁴⁴ http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/curators_guide.html#id17

⁴⁵ <http://tinyurl.com/cleantoolids>

⁴⁶ <https://www.openapis.org/>

⁴⁷ <http://portal.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=932295>

OpenTrials API	https://bio.tools/tool/OpenTrials_API/version/none
BridgeDb API	https://bio.tools/tool/BridgeDb_API/version/none
WikiPathways API	https://bio.tools/tool/WikiPathways_API/version/none
Proteins API	https://bio.tools/tool/Proteins_API/version/none
OpenPHACTS API	https://bio.tools/tool/Open_PHACTS_API_Swagger/version/none

Table 4. Database APIs imported using OpenAPI-Importer.

6.6 Portal software

All components were adapted to support the stable data model (Section 6.3, Appendix B). Various additional improvements were made (described below), including improvements to the basic system and new features in response to feedback from end-users and partners.

6.6.1 Registration interface

New developments include:

- refactoring to support the stable data model
- pane to provide interactive JSON format editing with inline error reporting

The features for adding & editing content remain somewhat primitive, and are greatly improved in the new tool annotator prototype (Appendix G.6) that will be moved into production in due course.

6.6.2 Query interface

6.6.2.1 Search bar

New developments include:

- support for faceted search over "Collection" and "Credit"
- clean up of drop-down suggestions which now properly resolve when clicked
- much improved searching mechanism, including exact searches using quotes

6.6.2.2 Summary view

New developments include:

- refactoring to support the stable data model

6.6.2.3 Grid view

New developments include:

- refactoring to support the stable data model
- cleaner look and feel

6.6.2.4 Tool Cards

New developments include:

- refactoring to support the stable data model

- new, modern look, cleaner than before (Fig. 7)
- introduction of Altmetrics bookmarklet for tools which have an Altmetric result
- action buttons for requesting ownership or edit rights

Figure 7. Tool Cards. Fresh look with Altmetric widget (publication information) rendered in top-right corner.

6.6.2.5 Literature integration

Software developments to expose literature data in bio.tools include:

- use of the AltMetric bookmarklet

Left as future work:

- rendering basic information for tool publications, in copy-pastable form
- inclusion of citation counts
- sorting bio.tools entries by citation count and AltMetric attention score

6.6.3 Entry management

Improvements include:

- New content ownership and permissions model (Section 6.6.3.2)
- New bio.tools subdomains for promoting individual tool collections (Section 6.6.3.3)
- New myProfile pages for user's entry and subdomain management (Section 6.6.3.1)

6.6.3.1 MyProfile pages

New MyProfile pages (Fig. 8) are available to every registered user and display the user’s tools and tools shared with them.

Figure 8. MyProfile pages.

6.6.3.2 Content ownership / permissions model

The revised system envisioned in D1.1 has been implemented. The (conflated) notion of affiliation and entry owner in the old system is gone, with a proposed new credit mechanism (Appendix H.5) for managing credits formerly associated “affiliation”. The “owner” (original registrant) of a bio.tools entry can update an entry, *i.e.* edit its annotations or delete an entry, but can now share edit rights with specific account holders or make ownership public, in a similar way to Google documents (Fig. 9). Any logged-on user may request edit rights or ownership *via* buttons in the Tool Cards.

Figure 9. Entry sharing during registration.

A user can transfer ownership to other users, or disown an entry in which case it becomes owned by bio.tools admin. These features are made available *via* the “Requests” pane (Fig. 10) visible to logged-on users.

Figure 10. “Requests” pane for handling entry ownership or edit requests.

6.6.3.3 Subdomains

Following multiple requests for local views of bio.tools content and means to promote individual collections, we have partially implemented the proposal described in D1.1. Any user can now create a bio.tools subdomain; the bio.tools homepage prefiltered to show only specific entries. Tooling in a user’s MyProfile (Section 6.6.3.1) allows a user to create a subdomain and conveniently populate it with tools *via* various search features (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Subdomain management features.

Subdomains follow the scheme:

{subdomainID}.bio.tools

where {subdomainID} is the unique identifier of a bio.tools subdomain user-supplied upon creation. Subdomain hierarchy is not supported however institutional structure can easily be handled by following consistently a subdomain naming pattern, *e.g.*

denbi.bio.tools	(tools from <i>all</i> de.NBI nodes)
denbi-gcbn.bio.tools	(tools from a de.NBI node)
denbi-bioinfra.pro	(tools from another de.NBI node)

There is scope to improve upon and extend the subdomain functionality (Appendix H.4).

6.6.4 Back-end architecture

6.6.4.1 Back-end database

This was refactored to support the stable data model.

6.6.4.2 Account management

Improvements include:

- automailer with smoother verification (for account creation) and password reset process

6.6.4.3 Administrator tooling

New developments include:

- bio.tools accounts may receive a designated “bio.tools admin” status, allowing edit rights of *any* entry *via* the registration/editing interface
- support added to allow programmatic updates *via* iPython notebooks⁴⁸
- mock-up of a new curators interface (Appendix G.7) for validating bio.tools entries as per the emerging information standard

6.6.4.4 Tool IDs and persistent URLs

The tool identifier scheme described in D1.1 aimed to provide a persistent reference to versions of tools with unique functionality (*i.e.* different primary inputs, outputs or operations), with Tool Card URLs of the form:

`https://bio.tools/{toolID}/{versionID}`

where `toolID` is the unique identifier of a tool (a URL-safe derivative of the tool name) and `versionID` is the unique identifier of a tool version (a URL-safe derivative of the supplied version label). This did not work out in practice:

- users created new entries for versions of software with trivial functional differences only and/or merely to record the version number had changed

⁴⁸ <https://ipython.org/notebook.html>

- quite often (but inconsistently) new tool versions have different names, thus the `toolID` is different for such cases, breaking the scheme
- some types of tools (e.g. Web applications) do not (generally) have a version number, and sometimes tools that should have them, don't
- version labels are highly diverse syntactically, resulting in a non-trivial mapping of version label to ID

The result was a great deal of redundancy and unnecessary complexity, especially given that are approximately only 100 or so *bona fide* different tool versions (as defined by unique functionality) are currently registered. The data thus supports a light touch only, which is more sustainable given the available resources and anyway, fine-grained version information is already managed well in sites such as GitHub.

For these reasons, we have dropped version information from the entry reference, and now use a simpler scheme:

```
https://bio.tools/tool/{toolID}
https://bio.tools/{toolID}
```

For example:

<https://bio.tools/tool/signalp>

<https://bio.tools/signalp>

Both forms are supported in anticipation that other types of end point (notably for bio.tools contributors, see Appendix H.4) may be needed, and demarcated from the toolID namespace.

It's still possible to register different versions of tools and record the version number. In case different versions are registered, the requirement would be (as currently is often the case) to capture version information in the tool name and thus toolID, e.g. "mytool 2.0". Planned developments will

- allow a user to formally define relationships between entries, including that "entryA isNewVersionOf entryB" (Appendix H.9)
- associate a version label with a publication

"Cool URIs"⁴⁹ are a unique selling point of bio.tools, and thus the Tool Card URIs must be intuitive and human-readable. In practice, there are challenges to delivering this that are being addressed (Section 6.5.4.2).

6.6.4.5 API

New developments include:

- support for the stable data model
- support for the new tool identifier scheme
- improved SEO based with correctly associated metadata (keywords, titles and descriptions)

⁴⁹ <https://www.w3.org/Provider/Style/URI>

6.6.4.6 Search architecture

The performance of the search bar was intensively critiqued with subsequent improvements to the parameterisation of the Elastic search engine. Further rounds of critique and optimisation are needed and will be done as a future work (Appendix H.7).

6.6.4.7 QC mechanism

D1.1 envisioned a Quality Control / Quality Assurance (QC/QA) mechanism. This has been partly implemented in an automated system that performs and reports on various QC checks, including:

- broken links
- duplicate homepage URLs
- use of top-level EDAM concepts
- use of deprecated EDAM concepts
- input, output or publication not specified

Reporting is made directly in the database, with API endpoints providing error information in JSON format, on a per tool basis or for all tools. Development of the QC/QA mechanism is planned (Appendix H.1).

6.6.5 Project metrics

The automatic monitoring and reporting to <https://bio.tools/stats> of registry statistics has been enhanced to provide finer-grained details of content growth and change, in support the portal consolidation and expansion phases. This includes:

- number of annotations and growth over time
- breakdown of annotations by groups defined in the information standard (Section 6.4, Appendix C)
- contributors by top-level domain

More stats will be added in due course⁵⁰.

6.7 Future Work

There are major challenges to deliver the desired “endgame” for registry (Section 1) that can only be addressed through a comprehensive approach, involving development of all aspects of the project, notably:

- targeted actions to improve metadata quality, including content review and clean-up (Section 6.5.4)
- more accessible curation mechanisms
- clear information standards that motivate and support quality improvements
- better quality assurance and control process
- better engagement with and leverage of tool developers, service providers and other contributors
- curation guidelines and other documentation to facilitate contributions

Much of the future work is directed towards these ends. A summary of high-level tasks mostly in the “bio.tools features” and “bio.tools content” strands of sifterapp that have been assigned

⁵⁰ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/243>

“Critical” or “High” priority are summarised in Table 5. A summary of some of these tasks is given in Appendix H.

Beyond these tasks, there were many positive suggestions raised from the EXCELERATE midterm review process that are informing the future development plans of the portal. These will be worked up into formal options and recommendations by 2017 Q4.

Tracker ⁵¹	Task	Section	Priority	Expected delivery date
bio.tools features	Expose bio.tools for indexing by Google https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/66 https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/240	-	Critical	2017 Q4
bio.tools features	Improved QA / QC process https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/117	Appendix H.1	High	2017 Q4
bio.tools features	Drive-by curation https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/437	Appendix H.2	High	2018 Q1
bio.tools features	Implement Tool Annotator based on prototype https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/211	Appendix G.6	High	2018 Q1
bio.tools features	Usage monitoring & reporting https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/369	-	Normal	2018 Q1
bio.tools features	Handling benchmarking & monitoring metrics https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/309	-	High	2018 Q2
bio.tools features	Crosslinking bio.tools & TeSS https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsregistry/issues/80 https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/216	-	High	2018 Q2
bio.tools features	“Sandbox” for intermediate registrations https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/107	Appendix H.3	High	2018 Q2
bio.tools features	Implement curators interface based on mock-up https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/435	Appendix G.7	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools features	Contributor Cards & enhanced subdomains https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/432	Appendix H.4	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools features	Improved credits mechanism https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/431	Appendix H.5	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools features	Implement basic UI improvements following the prototypes https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/427	Appendix G.1, G.2, G.3	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools features	Support information standard https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/425 https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/439	Appendix H.6	High	2018 Q3

⁵¹ one of the 10 task strands defined in <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/>

bio.tools features	Implement Topics view based on prototype https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/172	Appendix G.4	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools features	Improved search and filtering https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/37	Appendix H.7	High	tbd
bio.tools features	Support for stable schema (phase 2 of 3) https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/433	Appendix H.9	Normal	tbd
Benchmark & monitor	Software quality metrics https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/203	Appendix H.8	High	tbd
bio.tools content	Complete clean-up tool names IDs https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/401	Section 6.5.4.2	Critical	2017 Q3
bio.tools content	Complete clean-up EDAM Topic & Operation annotations https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/156	-	Critical	2017 Q3
bio.tools content	Coverage of ExPASy https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/33	-	Critical	2017 Q3
bio.tools content	MyBioSoftware coverage https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/356	-	Critical	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	Complete consolidation of duplicate entries https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/297	Section 6.5.4.1	Critical	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	Improved tool descriptions https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/338	-	High	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	Coverage of NAR databases edition https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/246	-	High	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	Improve msutils.org to “gold” standard https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/177	-	High	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	RNA analysis tools https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/62	-	High	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	Refactor content towards “canonical” entries (planning) https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/40	-	High	2017 Q4
bio.tools content	Improve consistency of EDAM annotations (planning) https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/409	-	High	2018 Q1
bio.tools content	Metabolomics tools https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/279	-	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools content	Curation of Node proposal services to high standard https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/189	-	High	2018 Q3
bio.tools content	Outreach / assign tools to rightful owners https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/171	-	High	2018 Q3

Table 5. Future work

Appendix A: Community details

A.1 Events

Here we list events (Table 6) in which ELIXIR personnel participated in order to develop or promote the portal. All events are listed online⁵².

Type	Name	Date / location	Description
Conference	ELIXIR-DK @ IMSB 2016	Jul 8-12 2016, Orlando, USA	ELIXIR-DK had a booth at IMSB 2016 to showcase the work of the Danish ELIXIR node including the ELIXIR Tools & Data Services Registry (bio.tools) and the EDAM ontology. https://www.iscb.org/ismb2016
Workshop	ELIXIR-DK / bio.tools Open Day	Aug 24 2016, Syddansk Universitet, DK	An informal day of presentations, discussion and hacking, combining two events in one: 1) ELIXIR-DK staff technical get-together and 2) bio.tools workshop. http://tinyurl.com/registryhackathon9
Conference	ELIXIR-DK @ 2nd Annual Danish Bioinformatics Conference	Aug 25-26 2016, Odense, DK	ELIXIR-DK presented a booth. http://www.conferencemanager.dk/DKBiC-2016/home.html
Conference	ELIXIR-DK @ ECCB	Sep 3-7 2016, The Hague, NL	ELIXIR-DK presented a booth. http://www.eccb2016.org/
Workshop	bio.tools & EDAM @ 1st NEUBIAS taggathon	Sep 14-16 2016, Barcelona, ES	The 1st NEUBIAS Taggathon hosted and supported by Universitat Pompeu Fabra, organized by the working group "Webtool" (WG4) of NEUBIAS, and in conjunction with the NEUBIAS training school. The aim was to bring-in pre-incubated ideas and elements of the next biii.info/BISE webtool and to progress with its implementation. The presence of bio.tools and EDAM projects ensured coordination of NEUBIAS and EuroBioimaging registry and ontology developments with ELIXIR. http://eubias.org/NEUBIAS/?page_id=228
Technical	bio.tools @ NETTAB	Oct 24 2016, Rome, IT	A one day bioinformatics hackathon organized by ELIXIR held in occasion of the NETTAB 2016 Workshop. The hackathon will include the following two main strands: 1) Biosoftware description using bio.tools and schema.org. 2) Deployment of bioinformatics tools and services through Docker. http://www.igst.it/nettab/2016/programme/hackathon/ http://tinyurl.com/registryhackathon10
Thematic	Computational Proteomics Resources	Jan 10-13, 2017, Semmering, AT	A thematic hackathon aimed at curating tools for computational proteomics, co-located with the Computational Proteomics Conference. http://tinyurl.com/registryhackathon11

⁵² <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/events.html>

Workshop	bio.tools @ Debian Med Sprint	Jan 12-16 2017, Bucharest, RO	bio.tools folk join the Debian Med folk for co-hacking and co-learning. We improved EDAM annotations in Debian Med, and progressed towards importing high-quality software information from Debian (Med) to bio.tools. https://wiki.debian.org/Sprints/2017/DebianMed2017
Thematic	Genomics tools in crop & animal breeding	Feb 2-3 2017, Aarhus, DK	A curation hackathon aimed at curating software tools used for crop and animal breeding research. http://tinyurl.com/registryhackathon12
Workshop	bio.tools & EDAM @ 2nd NEUBIAS taggathon	Feb 13-15 2016, Oeiras near Lisbon, PT	The 2nd NEUBIAS Taggathon hosted and supported by the Gulbenkian Institute of Science, organized by the working group "Webtool" (WG4) of NEUBIAS, and in conjunction with the NEUBIAS training school and the following NEUBIAS conference. We extended the bioimaging sub-domain of EDAM in team work with bioimaging experts, and coordinated the development of biii.info/BISE with bio.tools. http://eubias.org/NEUBIAS/what-is-taggathon/taggathon-2-gulbenkian-oeiras/
Workshop	ELIXIR discovery portals	Feb 27-28 2017, Helsinki, FI	ELIXIR Innovation and SME Forum: Genomics and Health - Global resources for local Innovation. The forum was aimed at the companies that use public bioinformatics resources in their business and would like to further streamline this process. The event was jointly organized by ELIXIR Finland, ELIXIR Estonia and the ELIXIR Hub. bio.tools was presented. https://www.elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-innovation-and-sme-forum%3A-genomics-and-health-global-resources-local-innovation
Workshop	The future of proteomics in ELIXIR	Mar 1-2 2017, Tübingen, DE	Focussed on creating a white paper to discuss the common infrastructures and services needed by the European proteomics community. bio.tools and EDAM were discussed. https://www.elixir-europe.org/events/strategic-workshop-future-proteomics-elixir
Technical	Visual Workflows in bio.tools	Mar 1-3 2017, Tallin, EE	A three day workshop organised by ELIXIR-EE and partners aiming to implement a proof-of-principle for "visual workflows" in bio.tools : navigation of bio.tools content with cross-links to TeSS via diagrams for common analytical workflows. http://tinyurl.com/registryhackathon13

Table 6. Events where bio.tools was promoted or developed.

A.2 Thematic Editors

The sheer number of software and continuous advancements in tool development demand extensive and sustained efforts to provide comprehensive annotations. Such challenge can be overcome by distributing the curation effort across a network of engaged and experienced partners, which contribute to improve bio.tools content and to adjust the EDAM vocabulary to the needs of the respective communities. Careful coordination of the distributed tasks is required to keep similar quality standards and increase tool interoperability.

Thematic editors (Table 7) are well connected with their respective scientific community, experts in their field, have a broad knowledge about commonly used software and are motivated to promote bio.tools. The following *tasks* will enforce an improvement to the bio.tools content:

- Review of bio.tools and EDAM to survey conceptual and semantic coverage
- Development of a strategy to achieve and sustain a minimum information level, as per the emerging information standard (Section 6.4, Appendix C). Updates and documentation have been provided through assigned Sifterapp issues (e.g. RNA analysis tools⁵³, proteomics tools⁵⁴, livestock and plant tools⁵⁵ and Metabolomics tools⁵⁶)
- Engage with their community, supervise hackathons and promote bio.tools in general
- Mentor a student for practical work such as manual curation
- Implement sustainable procedures for systematic tool reviews (e.g. bio.tools alert service) and curation standards

Benefit: A thematic editorships provides the opportunity to become a documented expert. Editors will acquire extensive knowledge and experience about available software in their fields e.g. to publish high-quality reviews. The editors will train additional experts during training and curation events (e.g. hackathons) as well as *via* student supervision. Moreover, the ELIXIR framework will support them to apply for further funding to amplify their activities within their field (at least, this will be pursued).

Anne Wenzel	RNA structure
Jon Ison	General purpose sequence analysis
Jose M. Carazo	Electron microscopy, structural biology
Josep Gelpí	Structural bioinformatics
Jürgen Haas	Protein structural biology, structural bioinformatics
Marta Villegas	Natural language processing
Martin Krallinger	Text Mining, natural language processing, named entity recognition
Reza Salek	Metabolomics
Veit Schwämmle	Proteomics, statistics
Vivi R. Gregersen	Agricultural science (association analysis, genomics)

Table 7. Current thematic editors.

A *studentship* (Section 6.2.3.3) to support thematic editing comprises (at least) one full month of full working hours which are mostly distributed over a longer time period. Applications are written on basis of the template⁵⁷ (see e.g. proteomics studentship⁵⁸). The students are recruited after dissemination *via* GitHub⁵⁹, project mailing lists *etc.*

⁵³ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/62>

⁵⁴ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/177>

⁵⁵ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/178>

⁵⁶ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/279>

⁵⁷ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/thematic_editing.pdf

⁵⁸ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/proteomics_software.pdf

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships>

Appendix B: Improvements in biotoolsSchema 2.0.0

Improvements made over the candidate stable schema (described in D1.1) in the production of biotoolsSchema 2.0.0 include revision of attributes and controlled vocabularies.

B.1 Attributes

The following changes were made to the candidate stable schema described in D1.1:

- `commandLineSpec` attributes (details of the command-line interface to a tool) dropped: such information will not be maintained in bio.tools, but will be extracted from appropriate sources and combined with bio.tools metadata as a function of the Workbench Enabler Service (described in D1.6 report).
- `image` attributes (for virtual machine or container information) amalgamated into refactored `download` grouping
- `elixirInfo` attributes (information for ELIXIR internal purposes) added, from a collaboration with ELIXIR Hub
- `summary` attributes simplified by moving links to `link` group, and with better modelling of software version information (now supporting both version labels and unique identifiers)
- `function` attributes refactored to allow specification of EDAM concepts by either or both of EDAM terms or URIs
- `status` attribute (describing miscellaneous status of the software) refactored into separate `maturity`, `cost` and `accessibility` elements to improve usability
- `download` attributes (link to a download for the software, e.g. source code, virtual machine image or container) now supports specification of useful command pertinent to the download, e.g. for getting or installing a tool.
- `contact` attributes (details of primary point(s) of contact, e.g. person, helpdesk or mailing list.) simplified, removing contact type or role information (now modelled in `credit`)
- `credit` elements (an individual or organisation that should be credited for the software) extensively revised to allow more comprehensive and flexible specification of contact information

B.2 Controlled vocabularies

biotoolsSchema 2.0.0 defines 16 controlled vocabularies:

- **tool type** (the type of application software)
- **operating system** (the operating system supported by a downloadable software package)
- **programming language** (name of programming language the software source code was written in)
- **license** (software or data usage license)
- **relation type** (between this and another registered software)
- **maturity** (how mature the software product is)
- **cost** (monetary cost of acquiring the software)
- **accessibility** (whether the software is freely available for use)

- **link type** (the type of data, information or system that is obtained when the link is resolved)
- **download type** (type of download that is linked to)
- **documentation type** (type of documentation that is linked to)
- **publication type** (type of publication)
- **entity type** (types of entities that may be credited)
- **entity role** (roles that may be assigned to creditable entities)
- **disk image format** for virtual machine
- **containers formats**

Appendix C: Candidate tool information standard

The standard is based on biotoolsSchema, but goes beyond the syntactic / semantic constraints that can be defined in a XML schema. It has two parts:

- a list of *what* tool attributes must be specified, or stated as not being available, at various tiers of entry *completeness*
- a set of Curation Guidelines describing *how* each attribute should be specified, to provide annotation *quality*

The standard will be implemented in bio.tools through:

- an entry verification process (Appendix C.2)
- labelling of entries according to adherence to the standard (Appendix C.3)
- minimum requirements for entry registration and visibility (Appendix C.4)

C.1 Attributes in the standard

Attributes (defined in biotoolsSchema) considered in the standard are shown (Fig. 12). Noteworthy features are:

- **Attribute groups.** Some attributes are grouped for purposes of determining adherence to the standard. For example to achieve a tick for "Documentation" at least one of "General documentation", "API documentation" or "API specification" must be specified.
- **Applicability and availability of attributes.** An attribute only counts towards the rating if, in fact, it is both applicable to that type of tool (see below) and actually available. In case an attribute is applicable but not available, a positive statement to that effect will be required during registration to get a tick for that attribute, *e.g.* the user would need explicitly to specify "a publication is not available" for "Publication".
- **Applicability.** Not all attributes are applicable to all types of tool, *e.g.* source code is not normally available for database portals. Applicability would (ideally) be formally defined on a tool type-specific basis or (otherwise) left to the wit of the curator. The latter option may be more realistic given the complexities and edge cases. An applicability matrix (attributes versus tool types) would however lay the foundation for a more sophisticated, future standard better reflecting the specific information requirements of each type of tool.

	😊	🙂	😄	🌟
Name	✓	✓	✓	✓
Description	✓	✓	✓	✓
Homepage	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tool type	✓	✓	✓	✓
Unique ID	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific topics	✓	✓	✓	✓
Publication*	✓	✓	✓	✓
Contact information	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific operations		✓	✓	✓
Documentation →		✓	✓	✓
Operating system*		✓	✓	✓
Type of input & output data*			✓	✓
Code availability →			✓	✓
Accessibility →			✓	✓
Supported data formats*				✓
Community →				✓
Downloads →				✓

→ Documentation	
General	
API documentation*	At least one
API specification*	

→ Code availability	
Repository*	
Source code*	At least one
Source package*	
License*	✓
Language*	✓

→ Accessibility	
Terms of use*	At least one
Accessibility	
Cost	✓

→ Community	
Helpdesk*	✓
Issue tracker*	✓
Mailing list*	✓

→ Downloads	
Binaries*	
Binary package*	
Container file*	At least one
VM image*	
CWL file*	
Tool wrapper (galaxy)*	
Tool wrapper (taverna)*	At least one
Tool wrapper (other)*	

* if applicable and available. Not all attributes apply to all tool types. In case an attribute is applicable but not available, the entry must state this.

Figure 12. Attributes in the information standard.

C.2 Verification process

Adherence of entries to the standard will be verified *via* a new curators interface (Appendix G.7) that will enable a bio.tools curator to validate entries according to QC checks (from the Curation Guidelines), including:

- automated checks (by bio.tools system)
- checks which must be done manually (by bio.tools curators)

To ensure the verification process is efficient, scalable and fair, every user should be allowed to verify their own entries, but with trusted users (specifically bio.tools admin and possibly Thematic Editors) allowed to verify *any* entries. The requirement is effective tooling for this,

such that a curator can tick-off guidelines that have been satisfied. A verification date is needed and also a way to indicate whether the entry has been updated since it was verified (e.g. by changing the colour of the stamp).

C.3 Entry labelling

Entries will be labelled as per adherence to the standard:

- a label for the 5 tier rating of annotation completeness (Fig. 13), based on what attributes are given
- an additional "Verified" label (Fig. 14) if all attributes pass QC checks (automated & manual)

The "Verified" label will be date stamped, or otherwise rendered in such a way (e.g. by colour) to indicate verifications that are old and/or entries that have subsequently been updated. Exactly how to do this needs to be planned carefully so the value of the label is not deprecated. In addition, for certain attributes (notably publication and license) it could be useful to know (by bio.tools admin, and possibly users) when an attribute was stated as being "Not available". This could help inform periodic updates of the registry. Beyond this, great care is needed to avoid misunderstanding of the user, who could confuse the labelling of entry completeness and quality with a rating of the tool quality itself.

An early version used a 5-star labeling, but this was replaced with clean emoticons and adjectives which express (unlike stars) that an entry being labelled in a lower tier is not a bad thing.

Figure 13. Entry completeness labelling.

Figure 14. Entry verification labelling.

C.4 Minimum requirements

The standard provides the basis for practical minimum information requirements in various scenarios, including:

- minimum standard for *any* registration : tentatively “NEEDS TO IMPROVE”
- minimum standard to be set *visible* in bio.tools: tentatively “OKAY”

The latter will be implemented as part of the “sandbox” for intermediate registration (Appendix H.3).

C.5 Handling change

The standard must necessarily be open to change (at least somewhat) in years to come in light of experience and feedback, however we must handle change very carefully, especially to ensure *e.g.* that an entry labelled today as “EXCELLENT” does not suddenly become “NEEDS TO IMPROVE”. There are several options to handle that must be explored, including for examples improving such entries before applying any relabelling). In any case, potentially “breaking” changes to the standard will be restricted to once per year (*i.e.* as per biotoolsSchema).

Appendix D: EDAM Formats sub-ontology (planning)

This issue is tracked in sifter (<https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/111>). Actions to deliver a comprehensive and practical catalogue of data formats for the life sciences include:

- Multiple misc. addition / changes to Format concepts
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues>
- Refactoring of Format (by type of data)
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues/283>
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues/287>
- Better documentation of info. requirement for format requests
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontologyDocs/issues/4>
- Systematic review of existing format concepts as per criteria checklist, with considerations for consistency
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues/215>
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues/246>
- Ensure coverage for Galaxy applications
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues/85>
- Ensure coverage of BioSharing
 - <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/12>
- Misc. other additions managed internally by ELIXIR-NO
- Formats publication
 - <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/86>
- Workshop to advance this work
 - <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/220>

Appendix E: Tool collections

Work providing coverage of major tool collections is summarised below.

E.1 BioConductor

BioConductor⁶⁰ is a highly popular suite of tools (R packages) for the analysis and comprehension of high-throughput genomic data. BioConductor offers more than 1300 software packages, the metadata for which is rich, but of highly variable quality and with many inconsistencies owing, in part, to the lack of use of controlled vocabularies or syntactic constraints. The metadata were imported following a process that first mapped the BioConductor metadata fields to biotoolSchema attributes, followed by a semi-automated standardisation process, and format transformation for import. Subsequently 300 of the packages were annotated to an even higher standard manually, including data type and format annotations.

E.2 Bioinformatics Links Directory

Bioinformatics Links Directory⁶¹ features curated links to molecular resources, tools and databases. It contains 1548 tool and 621 database entries⁶² and has a significant overlap with the content of NAR Web Servers and Database Issues (Appendix E.3). All tools and databases that were accessible at the time and had publication information were added to bio.tools. Metadata from the Bioinformatics Links Directory were carried over to bio.tools with subsequent annotation of EDAM topics and operations done automatically using the EDAMmapper utility (Appendix J.1).

E.3 NAR Web Servers and Database Issues

Nucleic Acids Research (NAR) publishes the results of research on nucleic acids and related work. NAR Web Servers and Database Issues⁶³ contain 1222 tools and 305 databases (mostly already included in the Bioinformatics Links Directory). Combined, NAR Web Servers and Database Issues and Bioinformatics Links Directory contain 2113 unique resources of which >2000 are present in bio.tools. Some tools were omitted either due to being obsolete or not having any publications. EDAMmapper was again used to provide EDAM annotations.

E.4 SEQwiki

SEQwiki⁶⁴ is a wiki database featuring 700 next generation sequencing and genomics tools. Tools are tagged in various fields including application domain, bioinformatics method, input and output format *etc.* Similar to BioConductor, the tags represented a folksonomy and contained much redundancy and inconsistency. Import to bio.tool followed a process of schema mapping, and then iterations of revisions to EDAM and annotation of the tools, converging upon an optimal set of non-redundant EDAM Topic and Operation annotations. All other annotations (publications, licences, operating system, *etc.*) were standardised and transformed to conform to the bio.tools schema. 64 obsolete tools were identified and dropped.

⁶⁰ <https://www.bioconductor.org/>

⁶¹ https://bioinformatics.ca/links_directory/

⁶² 1483 unique tools and 569 databases

⁶³ https://bioinformatics.ca/links_directory/journals/nar

⁶⁴ <https://www.semantic-mediawiki.org/wiki/SEQwiki>

E.5 ExpASy

ExpASy⁶⁵ is the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics portal which provides access to 350 scientific databases and software tools in different areas of life sciences, including proteomics, genomics, evolutionary evolution, systems biology, population genetics and transcriptomics. The ExpASy and the bio.tools schemas were aligned, and the ExpASy keywords and categories mapped to EDAM topics and operations, in order to provide good quality annotation. The entire collection is staged for import into bio.tools.

E.6 msutils.org

msutils.org⁶⁶ is a list of free (gratis) software for analysis of mass spectrometry data. It is both a repository and a collection of up-to-date links to different types of freely available software and code snippets for the visualization and analysis of mass spectrometry data with emphasis on automated methods for proteomics and protein analysis. The list was initiated by Magnus Palmblad in 2007 and is still maintained - primarily - by him, but with many contributions and suggestions from the research community. In collaboration with bio.tools, a clean-up including removal of dead links, and systematic addition of literature references was concluded, with ~240 tools subsequently imported to bio.tools⁶⁷.

E.7 Tools used by trainers

A list of 100+ tools used by the EBI training team and by ELIXIR trainers in their training courses was enumerated, and subsequently hand-curated and registered^{68,69}.

E.8 GO tools

Tools used by the Gene Ontology consortium⁷⁰ were annotated and registered⁷¹.

E.9 Institut Pasteur Galaxy services

Galaxy is an open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biomedical research. The Galaxy instance at Institut Pasteur is public; more than 280 tools are made available, as online services, to ~700 registered users as well as anonymous users. Furthermore, Galaxy is used as an execution engine to launch on the Institut Pasteur cluster, complex tools or workflows requiring a custom web interface, including MetaGenSense⁷², NGphylogeny.fr, Booster⁷³ and Shaman⁷⁴. This approach allows efficient management of all required tools on a single server and decreases the development effort required for web applications. From the bio.tools perspective, the Institut Pasteur Galaxy server thus represents an ideal test case for the ReGaTE utility⁷⁵ (described in D1.6

⁶⁵ <http://www.expasy.org/>

⁶⁶ <http://www.ms-utils.org/wiki/pmwiki.php/Main/SoftwareList>

⁶⁷ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/28>

⁶⁸ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/60>

⁶⁹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/70>

⁷⁰ <http://www.geneontology.org/>

⁷¹ <https://bio.tools/?page=1&collectionID=GO%20Tools&sort=score&ord=desc>

⁷² <https://metagensense.web.pasteur.fr>

⁷³ <http://booster.c3bi.pasteur.fr/>

⁷⁴ <http://shaman.c3bi.pasteur.fr/>

⁷⁵ Doppelt-Azeroual, O., Mareuil, F., Deveaud, Kalaš, M., Soranzo, N., van den Beek, M., Grüning, B., Ison, J. and Ménager, H. (2017). ReGaTE: Registration of Galaxy Tools in Elixir. GigaScience, doi:10.1093/gigascience/gix022

report), a utility for *en masse* registration of services from Galaxy instances: all of the 280 services have been annotated and registered in bio.tools.

E.10 de.NBI tools and services

The German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure⁷⁶ (de.NBI) is a national infrastructure supported by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research providing comprehensive, high-quality bioinformatics services to users in life sciences research and biomedicine. The de.NBI network includes 40 projects run by 30 partners and organized in 8 Service Centers located all over Germany. de.NBI develops and maintains almost 100 bioinformatic services⁷⁷ for the human, plant and microbial research fields, with a de.NBI Cloud that offers compute resources to the research community. In collaboration with bio.tools, the de.NBI scientists have annotated and registered their services in bio.tools to a very high standard, and are using the subdomain mechanism (Section 6.6.3.3) to showcase their services.

Appendix F: Content clean-up

Various clean-ups (Table 8) of the registry content were completed.

Issue	Description of clean-up	#fixes (if applicable)
Duplicate entries	Consolidate duplicated tools by merging annotation of multiple entries which describe the same tool. This is a work in progress (see Section 6.5.4.1).	190
Orphaned entries	Ownership of entry is transferred from bio.tools admin to the rightful owner, <i>e.g.</i> the tool developer or provider of an online service. Work in progress.	34
Bad tool names & tool IDs	A name and ID conformant to the Curation Guidelines is assigned.	6452 ⁷⁸
Broken links	Replace with current (resolvable) link.	230
Vague EDAM topic and operation annotations	Replace with more specific EDAM term ⁷⁹ .	2060
Redundant topic annotations	Remove redundant topics from tool entries.	109
Problematic tool descriptions	Manually and automatically (where applicable) identify and fix tool descriptions.	5764
Incorrect contact information	Fix tools with inappropriate contacts.	120
Incorrect credit annotations	Fix instances of bad EMBOSS, DRCAT, BioCatalogue tools credit annotation.	756

⁷⁶ <https://www.denbi.de/>

⁷⁷ <https://www.denbi.de/services>

⁷⁸ This is a cumulative count of the *checks* (and in many cases *fixes*) of names and IDs.

⁷⁹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/156>

Invalid credit annotation	Remove credit instances where credit name is “see publication”.	213
Incorrect tool type annotation	Fix wrong entry tool-type.	4

Table 8. Content clean-ups.

Appendix G: Prototype user interface developments

G.1 bio.tools landing page (home page)

The new landing page (Fig. 15) provides a more appealing and convenient entry point to bio.tools. It includes:

- basic information including scope and objectives
- information about partners, demonstrating to users the commitment of a pan European group of respected institutions
- tables of topics and subtopics which are most popular according to bio.tools EDAM annotations: clicking on a (sub)topic opens the Topic-based navigation (see below). This allow users to quickly dive into the content without having to specify any predefined criteria.

The tables of topics will be initially populated, and subsequently maintained, through a manual process which reflects the EDAM hierarchy, the number of bio.tools entries annotated with topics, and the current importance of the topics in the scientific community. In light of user critique, the view, EDAM Topics branch and corresponding bio.tools entries will all be refactored periodically to ensure the view satisfies user expectations.

Home Menu | Login

bio.tools

A portal to bioinformatics tools and data services world-wide

The Tools & Data Services Registry provides essential scientific and technical information about analytical tools and data services for bioinformatics. The registry is provided by a community effort coordinated by the Danish node of ELIXIR - the European infrastructure for biological information.

Browse by popular topics

Sequence Analysis >

Show 1025 tools in this topic >

- Mapping >
- Phylogenetics >
- Phylogenomics >
- Probes and primers >
- Sequence assembly >
- Sequence composition, complexity and repeats >
- Structure analysis >

Proteins >

Show 856 tools in this topic >

- Enzymes >
- Gene and protein families >
- Membrane and lipoproteins >
- Protein expression >
- Protein interactions >
- Protein properties >
- Protein sites, features and motifs >
- Protein structure analysis >
- Transcription factors and regulatory sites >

Structure analysis >

Show 423 tools in this topic >

- Carbohydrates >
- Lipids >
- Nucleic acid structure analysis >
- Protein structure analysis >
- Small molecules >
- Structure prediction >

Molecular genetics >

Show 643 tools in this topic >

- Gene and protein families >
- Gene expression >
- Gene structure >
- Genetic variation >

Nucleic acids >

Show 753 tools in this topic >

- DNA >
- Nucleic acid sites, features and motifs >
- Nucleic acid structure analysis >
- RNA >

Other interesting topics

Function analysis >

Show 1025 tools in this topic >

Molecular interactions, pathways and networks >

Show 856 tools in this topic >

Protein sites, features and motifs >

Show 423 tools in this topic >

Network of well established institutions

DTU
Technical University of Denmark

UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN
University of Copenhagen

EMBL
European Molecular Biology Laboratory

AARHUS UNIVERSITY
Aarhus University

AALBORG UNIVERSITY DENMARK
Aalborg University

SDU
University of Southern Denmark

SIB
Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics

Institut Pasteur
Pasteur Institute

A truly international effort

Figure 15. New bio.tools landing page (home page).

G.2 Tool Cards

The Tool Cards are redesigned with a fresh look (Fig. 16) and including the search bar at the top of the page.

Figure 16. New-look Tool Cards (prototype).

G.3 Summary view (tool mini-cards)

The new summary view now comprises much cleaner **tool mini-cards** (see G.4) with basic information about relevant tools for a given search result; the list is updated dynamically upon new searches.

G.4 Topics view

The new **topics view** allows users to navigate bio.tools content by expanding the EDAM topics tree (the parts used by bio.tools) with precise control over the possible routes to take (Fig. 17). The navigation pane (top box) shows the currently selected topic

- **Current topic** giving the concept definition (from EDAM), the number of tools annotated with this term or its ancestors and a link to further information
- **Breadcrumbs** showing the history (route in EDAM hierarchy) that to the current topic, which can be clicked on to return to topics at a higher level.
- **Subtopics** for navigation and with tool counts
- **Tool mini-cards** (Appendix G.3).

Figure 17. New bio.tools topics view (prototype).

G.5 Grid view

The grid view (Fig. 18) - which is especially useful for a more detailed comparison between similar tools - has been updated to provide users with more control over the displayed content. All the possible displayable attributes are now easily accessible on the top of page, along with sorting options, allowing a user to easily customize what information is being displayed.

The screenshot shows a web interface for the bio.tools registry. At the top, there is a search bar with 'Nucleic Acid' entered and '1025 entries found'. Below the search bar are sorting options (Updated, Added, Name) and display options (Compact, Detailed). A 'Show' section contains various filters like Name, Version, Description, Function, Input, Output, Topic, etc. The main content is a grid view of tool annotations. The grid has columns for Name, Description, Function, and Topic. The tools listed include MMDB, NAPP, Newt-omics, Reactome Biomart, DOMMINO, and SignalP. Each tool entry provides a brief description, a list of functions, and a list of topics.

Name	Description	Function	Topic
MMDB	Mouse Multiple Tissue Metabolome Database: metabolomic database containing a collection of metabolites measured from multiple tissues from single mice. The datasets are collected using a single instrument and not integrated from literatures, which is useful for capturing the holistic overview of large metabolomic pathway.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Database comparison Data handling Mass spectra calibration Annotation Query and retrieval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metabolomics Small molecules Molecular interactions, pathways and networks Database management Proteomics experiment
NAPP	Nucleic Acid Phylogenetic Profile Database: classifies coding and non-coding sequences in a genome according to their pattern of conservation across other genomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nucleic acid sequence feature detection Over-representation analysis Nucleic acid structure prediction Gene expression profiling Nucleic acid folding analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functional, regulatory and non-coding RNA Structure prediction Nucleic acid sites, features and motifs Nucleic acids Nucleic acid structure analysis
Newt-omics	Database of data from the newt <i>Notophthalmus viridescens</i> . Newt-Omics aims to provide a comprehensive platform of expressed genes during tissue regeneration, including extensive annotations, expression data and experimentally verified peptide sequences with yet no homology to other publically available gene sequences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data retrieval Data handling Gene expression profiling Gene expression analysis Query and retrieval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gene transcripts Gene expression Model organisms Transcriptomics Database management
Reactome Biomart	A BioMart integration of Reactome protein annotations with PRIDE mass spectrometry data and COSMIC somatic mutations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data retrieval Protein modelling (mutation) Protein post-translation modification site prediction Query and retrieval Protein identification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Genetic variation Proteomics experiment Protein modifications Proteins Pathology
DOMMINO	Database of Macromolecular interactions. Includes interactions between protein domains, interdomain linkers, N- and C-terminal regions and protein peptides.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protein interaction network analysis Protein fold recognition Protein interaction network prediction Protein domain recognition Protein interaction prediction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protein folds and structural domains Molecular interactions, pathways and networks Protein interactions Small molecules Protein folding, stability and design
SignalP	Mouse Multiple Tissue Metabolome Database: metabolomic database containing a collection of metabolites measured from multiple tissues from single mice. The datasets are collected using a single instrument and not integrated from literatures, which is useful for capturing the holistic overview of large metabolomic pathway.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Database comparison Data handling Mass spectra calibration Annotation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metabolomics Small molecules Molecular interactions, pathways and networks

Figure 18. Revised grid view with new look and features.

G.6 Tool annotator

Following a mock-up described in M1.1.1, we have developed the **EDAM Tool Annotator**: a plugin for the bio.tools registry designed to assist users with the discovery and usage of EDAM Ontology concepts in the tool registration and annotation process. The EDAM Tool Annotator brings a number of improvements over the currently existing interface:

1. Display additional details on EDAM concept information to the user such as name, definition, exact and narrow synonyms and term URI (Fig. 19)
2. EDAM concept search by multiple properties such as: name, synonyms and definitions (Fig. 20)
3. EDAM concept fuzzy search in which the user can search and discover EDAM concepts similar to their search queries (Fig. 21)
4. EDAM tree branch filtering for easier display and navigation of term search results (Fig. 22)
5. EDAM concepts addition to the annotation list in an easier, more straightforward fashion (Fig. 23)

Next steps will include:

1. adding Term Requester feature: create a request for a new EDAM concept. The request can be sent *via* email or posted as a GitHub issue
2. provide examples of tools annotated with the currently selected EDAM term
3. misc. other features (tbd), user testing
4. deployment as component of bio.tools registration interface

The EDAM Tool Annotator is implemented using the same programming languages and libraries as the front-end side of the bio.tools registry, thus making the integration process a straightforward task. The current version (a working prototype) of the EDAM Tool Annotator can be evaluated at:

<http://people.binf.ku.dk/vzn529/eta/>

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "Topic *". On the left, there is a search bar containing "Genetic variation". Below it, under "Search By:", there are checkboxes for "Name", "Exact Synonyms", "Narrow Synonyms", and "Definition", with "Name", "Exact Synonyms", and "Narrow Synonyms" checked. Under "Show Siblings:", there are radio buttons for "All", "Similar", and "None", with "All" selected. In the center, a hierarchical tree of topics is displayed, with "Genetic variation" highlighted. On the right, there are two buttons: "Add Term To List" and "Request term". Below these buttons, the term information is displayed: "Name: Genetic variation", "Definition: Stable, naturally occurring mutations in a nucleotide sequence including alleles, naturally occurring mutations such as single base nucleotide substitutions, deletions and insertions, RFLPs and other polymorphisms.", "Exact Synonyms: DNA variation", "Narrow Synonyms: Mutation, Polymorphism, Somatic mutations", and "URI: http://edamontology.org/topic_0199".

Figure 19. Additional EDAM details. The displayed EDAM term information includes term name, definition, exact synonyms, narrow synonyms and term URI.

Topic *

Added topic terms (0):

Search By:
 Name
 Exact Synonyms
 Narrow Synonyms
 Definition

Show Siblings:
 All
 Similar
 None

▼ Topic
 ► Biology
 ► Biomedical science
 ► Chemistry
 ▼ Computational biology
 ► Function analysis
 ► Molecular genetics
 ► Molecular interactions, pathways and networks
 ▼ Nucleic acids
 ▼ DNA
 ▼ **DNA binding sites**
 Transcription factors and regulatory sites
 DNA mutation
 DNA packaging
 DNA polymorphism
 DNA replication and recombination
 DNA structural variation
 ▼ Nucleic acid sites, features and motifs
 ▼ **DNA binding sites**

Add Term To List Request term

Name:
DNA binding sites

Definition:
Nucleic acids binding to some other molecule.

Exact Synonyms:
[]

Narrow Synonyms:

- Matrix-attachment region
- Nucleosome exclusion sequences
- Restriction sites
- Ribosome binding sites
- Scaffold-attachment region
- Matrix/scaffold attachment region

URI: http://edamontology.org/topic_3125

Figure 20. Multiple EDAM term properties. The search over the phrase “nucleic acids binding” does not match any term names or synonyms but it does match a part of the definition of the EDAM topic term “DNA binding sites”.

Operations *

Added operation terms (0):

Differential gene expression analysis
 Synonyms: []
 The analysis, using any of diverse techniques, to identify genes that are differentially expressed under a given experimental setup.

Gene expression analysis
 Synonyms: [Gene expression data analysis, RNA-seq analysis, Microarray data analysis]
 Process (read and / or write) gene expression (typically microarray) data, including analysis of one or more gene expression profiles, typically to interpret them in functional terms.

Gene expression QTL analysis
 Synonyms: [Gene expression QTL profiling, eQTL profiling, Gene expression quantitative trait loci profiling]
 Combine classical quantitative trait loci (QTL) analysis with gene expression profiling, for example, to describe describe cis- and trans-controlling elements for the

Figure 21. Fuzzy search. Using fuzzy search and matching, the search text “analyse gene expression” matches multiple EDAM terms such as “Differential gene expression analysis”, “Gene expression analysis” and “Gene expression QTL analysis”.

Figure 22. Hide siblings not in the search result path. The term “DNA transcription” matches the EDAM operations tree in multiple places. Instead of showing all terms and paths that do not match the search term and unnecessarily cluttering the matches in the tree, EDAM Tool Annotator provides the option to hide term siblings which do not contribute to the search results by clicking “None” under the “Show siblings” options.

Figure 23. Add multiple terms. Using the same search box, tree browser and information display panel, the EDAM Tool Annotator allows selecting and adding multiple terms to the annotation list. Clicking the “Add Term To List” button adds the current selected concept to the list of annotation terms. In this example, the EDAM format terms “BED”, “CSV” and “XML” have been previously added and more terms such as “JSON” can further be included in the term list.

G.7 Curators interface

A new view (Fig. 24) for bio.tools curators (both normal users and also “super-user” with rights to make edits on any entries) will allow a curator to check for the adherence of entries (post-registration) to the tool information standards and fix issue. This includes fixing issues as listed in the emerging Curators Guide (Section 6.2.4):

- identified by automated QC checks (Section 6.6.4.7, Appendix H.1)
- that must be validated by manual inspection

Using the interface, a curator will:

- view tools owned by them and their current verification status
- View tools assigned to them for curation (“super-users” only)

and on a per tool basis:

- view list of automatically found issues
- view guidelines for each attribute
- repair problems directly
- mark each problem as fixed

The screenshot displays the SignalP Curator interface, which is used for editing tool metadata. It features a search bar at the top and a navigation menu. The main content area is divided into three sections, each with a status indicator (red, orange, or green) and a 'Mark as resolved' button.

- Homepage:** Status: Red (1). Current value: `http://deadlink.com`. Guidelines: Homepage of the software, or some URL, that best serves this purpose. The URL should resolve to a web page of information specific to the software.
- Description:** Status: Orange (7). Current value: `-Predicted Signal Peptide is a web service which allows users to search genes based on organisms and other criteria such as minimum signalp sum score, maximum signalp D score and minimum signalp pr`. Guidelines: Short and concise textual description of the software function.
- Name:** Status: Green (✓). Current value: `signalp-1.4.0`. Guidelines: Canonical software name assigned by the software developer or service provider.

At the bottom of the interface, there are 'Validate' and 'Save' buttons.

Figure 24. Curator interface (mock-up).

G.8 biotoolsSum (collections view) (prototype)

bio.toolsSum (Fig. 25) is an application that provides a quick overview of tools of a particular collection divided into meaningful categories by topics covered. Currently it contains several domains (DNA, RNA, protein and drugs) divided by the type of data (1D, 2D, 3D and xD), however, new topics can be added on request. Development version can be accessed at: <http://elixirczsum.azurewebsites.net/services>.

Figure 25. bio.tools Sum displaying the overview of ELIXIR-CZ tools.

- bio.tools Sum is based on javascript React library. All data are gathered from the bio.tools API, collectionID is used to limit the query results to a one particular collection. In future, the application will also include information about the tools' publications acquired by Europe PMC API.
- The initial objective was to replace static data about Czech tools and services (<https://www.elixir-czech.cz/services>) with a dynamic version. Now, however, it can be used for any other collection by specifying other collectionID.
- Upon completing the project, bio.tools Sum will be offered to all Elixir partners.

Appendix H: Description of future work

H.1 Improved QA / QC process

Additional QC checks will be added⁸⁰ to the QA system (Section 6.6.4.7) to include all checks labelled “Automatically verified” in the emerging Curators Guide (Section 6.2.4), this itself being revised in light of an ongoing systematic review of existing content (Section 6.5.4). All checks (“automatically verified” but also those which are labelled “manually verified”) will be supported in the curators interface (Appendix G.7) and (in the shorter term) by a human-readable webpage of error messages for use by bio.tools admin.

H.2 Drive-by curation

To make quality improvement more sustainable, highly convenient and open ways to contribute are required. The idea of “drive-by curation”⁸¹ could be highly effective, whereby edits including corrections and new annotations from *anyone* (without login) are supported. The edits would be processed according to the edit rights (which would need modifying to support this), either taking immediate effect or being stored later moderation / approval.

H.3 “Sandbox” for intermediate registrations

In D1.1 we described how several providers have partially annotated content and want to use the registration interface for community-based improvement. A registry “sandbox” was suggested, to allow viewing and editing of such content, and also as a means to boost content contributions: by preloading incomplete (therefore cheap) content, followed by mailout to tool owners requesting they complete the registration. This idea will now be taken forward⁸² by:

1. Defining an information standard for tools that includes, at the lowest tier of quality, a reasonable but easy to achieve minimum standard of information. This work (Appendix C) is in progress.
2. Hiding from view (at least by default, possibly adjustable by users) tools which do not achieve a certain tier of quality: this constitutes a practical “sandbox” functionality whilst avoiding technical complexity.

In principle, it could be possible to further, *i.e.* by allowing registrations of entries with no minimum standard of quality, hiding these from view until improved as per 2. above, but it’s unclear whether this is desirable. In any case, support for entry visibility and possibly having this adjustable by users is required.

H.4 Contributor Cards & enhanced subdomains

From the EXCELERATE midterm review, there were strong recommendations to focus on partnership with developers, to create a Europe-wide community of developers and that leveraging the tool developer community is vital to improve the sustainability of the effort. To these ends, better acknowledgement and promotion of the contributions of specific developers and developer communities in bio.tools could help. This could be achieved through bio.tools Contributor Cards⁸³ hosted at persistent end-points:

`https://bio.tools/contributorID`

⁸⁰ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/117>

⁸¹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/437>

⁸² <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/107>

⁸³ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/432>

where {contributorID} is the unique identifier (bio.tools username, or user-supplied ORCID or GRID ID) of a bio.tools contributor.

There is also the possibility to extend the subdomain mechanism to credited entities (Appendix H.5) in so far as these have unique IDs, providing subdomains of the type:

```
{contributorID}.bio.tools
```

We will explore supporting minimal subdomain customisation and branding, *e.g.* a logo, contributor metadata, and possibly bespoke default columns, in light of user requests⁸⁴. We will scope these ideas more, building upon ideas that were partly envisioned in M1.6 (resource metadata catalogue).

H.5 Improved credits mechanism

An entry owner may annotate the credits for a tool, as per the possibilities defined in the stable schema (including ORCID IDs for people and GRID IDs for institutions). In future, when annotating credits, an entry owner will be able to:

- credit an existing contributor from a global list
- add a new one, providing metadata as per the biotoolsSchema credits definition

Contributors *must* have a unique ID (one of bio.tools username, ORCID or GRID ID) to be added to the global list of contributors.

The anticipated behaviour⁸⁵ is that all contributors (with a unique ID) will be recognised by exposing metadata - including lists of tools credited to them - *via* new “Contributors Cards” and (possibly) *via* subdomains (Appendix H.4).

Other developments may include:

- automatic crediting of bio.tools registrants (to encourage contributions)
- linked maintenance of bio.tools account with contact & credit information (to improve sustainability of maintenance)

H.6 Support for tool information standard

To support the emerging tool information standard (Section 6.4) in bio.tools requires⁸⁶:

- improved QA/QC process and Curation Guidelines (Appendix H.1)
- curators interface for entry verification (Section G.7)
- labelling of entries based on annotation completeness and verification (Appendix C.3)
- applying the standard as minimum information requirements any registrations and for default entry visibility (Appendix C.4)

H.7 Improved search and filtering

Not all the improvements to the search functionality envisioned in D1.1 were implemented, and new requirements⁸⁷ were defined:

⁸⁴ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/190>

⁸⁵ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/431>

⁸⁶ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/425>

⁸⁷ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/37>

- support for easy filtering over appropriate fields, such as tool type, operating system, accessibility *etc.*
- support for boolean search operators
- support in the suggestions box for controlled vocabulary terms from biotoolsSchema
- smart support for EDAM synonyms
- better use of EDAM ontology hierarchy

It will not be possible to achieve all of this with the current resource available. Crucially, there must user experience evaluation and subsequent parameter optimisation of the search algorithm at each stage.

H.8 Software quality metrics

The information standard (Section 6.4, Appendix C) is the basis for a useful metric of *tool metadata quality* (Fig. 26). There have been many requests for metrics reflecting other facets of quality, as a way to rank and sort entries. This including quality of the tool itself (this more a concern of EXCELERATE WP2 and D1.6). We are investigating additional metrics⁸⁸ which can be calculated from existing bio.tools annotations, or which would require simple extension to software model, including:

- metrics for facets from attribute groupings in the information standard, e.g. community, documentation *etc.*
- metrics for project maturity⁸⁹
- metrics for software good practice⁹⁰
- metrics for FAIRness of tools⁹¹

Crucially (to avoid toxicity) any aggregated metrics used as a basis to label entries must be both **objective** and **transparent**.

Figure 26. Tool metadata quality metric. The final version would distinguish “verified” from “unverified” entries.

⁸⁸ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/203>

⁸⁹ <https://github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsregistry/issues/113>

⁹⁰ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/192>

⁹¹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/226>

H.9 Support for stable schema (phase 2 and 3)

We will complete the final two phases^{92,93} of support for the stable model in the back-end architecture, registration interface, query interface and API, migrating the registry content for compliance. This will add support for:

- tool DOIs (and other types of unique identifier)
- tool short descriptions (super-concise descriptions for use in UIs everywhere)
- SO (Sequence Ontology) concepts IDs
- GO (Gene Ontology) concepts IDs
- NCBI taxonomy IDs
- collection IDs (augmenting or replacing the *ad hoc* collection tags currently in use)
- tool relationships
- practical API specification (openAPI-compatible, see Section 6.5.5)

H.10 Tool function guidelines and modeling

Better guidelines⁹⁴ for annotating a tool's functionality are needed, for example, to clarify what to do in cases where a tool provides an option between doing one operation or another, or always performs certain operations. Beyond this, it may be necessary to revisit the modelling of input and output, especially in cases where a tool supports different ways to specify an input of a certain type beyond what is encodable by specification of data format. For example a tool which processes a molecular sequence which may be specified as a literal sequence or indirectly by identifier. These are complex technical issues with design decisions being made with the known use cases (from D1.1) firmly in mind, but also in support of emerging applications.

H.11 Deeper literature integration

There is scope for much deeper literature integration, which will be pursued in due course⁹⁵, primarily through building relationships with scientific publishers. Possible actions include:

- journals to encourage published articles are registered with us
- journals to alert bio.tools when a software article is published
- develop benevolent policy *re* software publications being registered
- data sharing, *e.g.* exposing bio.tools info / *e.g.* EDAM fields on publisher pages
- support EDAM annotations within journal pages (on publication)
- re-use of DOIs, *e.g.* as assigned to software by F1000
- links to publishers repos (*e.g.* F1000 published software goes in their GitHub)
- “micropublication” of registered software / bio.tools micro-publication channel

H.12 End-user support

It is clear (especially in light of feedback from midterm review) that support for end-users must be a high priority. We will prioritise Task 1.4: “User support and derived registry development” (below).

Task 1.4: “User support and derived registry development”

⁹² <https://tinyurl.com/biotooldatamodel>

⁹³ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/433>

⁹⁴ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/464>

⁹⁵ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/118>

This task will provide direct and indirect user support to deliver impact for ELIXIR end-users. Direct support will be achieved primarily by leveraging the existing and highly popular user bioinformatics forums (BioStars, BioPlanet *etc.*). A User-support specialist will patrol such forums and respond to questions in one of four ways:

- 1) Where resources answering to the Users needs exist in the registry, a link to them in the registry will be provided via our API.
- 2) Where resources exist in the registry, but the registry API cannot be used to answer the question directly, they will request new features of the API and in so doing drive development of the Query Interface.
- 3) Where an appropriate resource exists but has not been registered, they will request the appropriate registry curator add it to the registry.
- 4) Where a registered resource exists that is close, but not quite what is required, they will forward feature requests to the appropriate developers.

Appendix I: Strategy for integration of bio.tools with other resources

I.1 Resources for tool information

There are numerous resources (Table 9) that (are used to) independently maintain software metadata, which complement and should be more fully integrated with bio.tools. Our strategy is based upon the vision of bio.tools becoming a sustainable primary archive for basic tool metadata (Section 6.2.1).

Galaxy	An open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biomedical research. Thousands of online services over tools are available in the Galaxy public server and in the dozens of other publicly accessible Galaxy servers: https://galaxyproject.org/public-galaxy-servers/#deepTools
BioShaddock	A Docker registry for Bioinformatics (in process of merging with BioContainers) hosting Docker images dedicated to a broad spectrum of Biological communities as represented by the Biogenouest Western France network:. https://docker-ui.genouest.org/app/#/
BioContainers	A community-driven project to create and manage bioinformatics software containers: https://github.com/BioContainers
RainBio	A registry of virtualised tools & appliances (groups of tools) on the IFB cloud infrastructure: https://rainbio.france-bioinformatique.fr/catalogue/
Dockstore	An open platform for sharing Docker-based tools described with the Common Workflow Language used by the GA4GH: https://dockstore.org/

Debian Med	A "Debian Pure Blend" of software packages for free and open source software for medical imaging, bioinformatics, clinic IT infrastructure, and others within Debian OS: https://www.debian.org/devel/debian-med/
biii.info	Biii is a website for organizing bioimage analysis resources, with manually edited pages allowing a user to search tools, workflows and functions for bioimage analysis. It is maintained by the NEUBIAS cost action. http://biii.upf.edu/
Major institutional collections	For which metadata is already maintained locally including EBI Services ⁹⁶ , ExPASy ⁹⁷ and IFB Tools ⁹⁸ .
GitHub	GitHub is the prevalent code hosting platform for version control and collaboration. Many tool developers already maintain certain tool metadata directly in GitHub. https://github.com/

Table 9. Resource maintaining software metadata.

I.2 Technical requirements

There are generic requirements for a useful integration with bio.tools:

- provide **coverage in bio.tools** of all tools that have been made available as an online service, containerised, virtualised, packaged or included in above resources
- respect the **“document once” principle** and the rights of individual tool developers and institutes to maintain their tool metadata wherever they wish including directly in bio.tools but elsewhere *e.g.* GitHub: all this in so far as is efficient and achievable, there are major challenges (see below).
- ensure **consistent tool descriptions** in bio.tools and other resources
- ensure a **sustainable maintenance mechanism** for upkeep of coverage and consistency
- support the **re-use of bio.tools data** and cross-linking, where possible and desirable, by other resources to help establish **bio.tools as the primary archive** of basic tool metadata

The technical requirements include:

- mapping the metadata schema of the resources and bio.tools
- mapping entries in the resources and bio.tools, which in turn implies a mapping of package, container, and service names to tool names stored in bio.tools
- efficient mechanism to create new bio.tools entries as required to provide - and maintain - coverage of resources, conformant to at least a minimum acceptable quality as per the emerging information standard for tools (Section 6.4, Appendix C)
- an efficient mechanism to allow resource managers to update bio.tools, specifying certain attributes across, in principle, all entries whilst respecting the notion of entry

⁹⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/services>

⁹⁷ <https://www.expasy.org/>

⁹⁸ <https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/en/services/tools>

ownership and edit rights. Such attributes include links to an online service for a tool, links out e.g. to BioContainers, download links, installation commands etc.

- unique identifiers and thus Tool Card URLs (Section 6.6.4.4) that provide a persistent reference to unique tools and resolve to a “canonical” tool description
- systematic refactoring of existing bio.tools content to ensure
 - duplicates entries are consolidated (Section 6.5.4.1)
 - supplied tool names and thus toolIDs are sensible (Section 6.5.4.2)
 - entries for canonical tools are included for tools underlying online services registered thus far⁹⁹
- common or at least compatible metadata exchange formats with shims (transformer utilities) as needed

I.3 Challenges

In principle, a further future possibility is that tool providers host tool metadata directly in webpages via the emerging tool biotoolsSchema-compatible specification for schema.org, being coordinated by BioSchemas. Were *basic tool metadata* to be maintained outside of bio.tools, efficient and sustainable synchronisation mechanisms would be needed to ensure the metadata remains consistent and up-to-date everywhere. Various approaches have been discussed, however this is a complex issues that must be explored more, including at future workshops. Options include:

- implement “read only” bio.tools entries, *i.e.* entries which are imported automatically and periodically from other resources, but which cannot be subsequently edited by other means (including the bio.tools API and UI)
- implement a tool metadata “diff” mechanism, *i.e.* tooling to allow bio.tools admin (and resource maintainers) to conveniently see differences and (in the case of bio.tools admin) merge in changes
- do not support import of basic tool metadata, rather, improve bio.tools (in all aspects) to ensure that it provides adequate primary archive functions for re-use by others, with dependencies that are 1. easy to make and 2. remain stable

Given the core aim of bio.tools (Section 1) is to provide a registry of unique “canonical” tool descriptions, there are many technical challenges, which might favour simply the latter option, and which need to worked out before implementation could begin:

- specific mappings of resource metadata to biotoolsSchema
- efficient handling of changes to schema of resources and bio.tools, including content refactoring
- how technically is synchronisation maintained, with new metadata registrations and updates from each side
- how to remove duplicates within the entire corpus
- How to ensure persistent references (URLs)
- how imports would work with respect to the bio.tools information standard (Section 6.4, Appendix C) including entry labelling and quality control (Section 6.6.4.7, Appendix H.1)

⁹⁹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/40>

- interface requirement to allow a user to register their content location in bio.tools, to make the system more generic and scalable to a greater number of partners

I.4 Next steps

Technical developments to fulfill the requirements (above) is ongoing on all fronts^{100,101} and will be advanced in due course, including at a forthcoming workshop (Oct 2017, France) which will focus on consolidation of BioShaddock and BioContainers and integration with bio.tools.

Following feedback from the ELIXIR EXCELERATE midterm review, we agree completely with the reviewers strong recommendation, to the effect that leveraging the tool developer community is vital to improve the sustainability of the effort. The work described helps to support that goal however the current resource provision and allocation within EXCELERATE WP1 is *not* commensurate to the task: we are exploring possible solutions to this which could include seeking additional funding *via* an ELIXIR Implementation Study and/or revision to the WP1 resource allocation and deliverables.

Appendix J: Tooling

J.1 edamMap

Following a barebones implementation mention in M1.1.1, we have developed the **edamMap utility**: a Java based software that helps curators to automatically create bio.tools entries based on various input information. It uses EDAM ontology for describing bioinformatics tools with terms from Topic, Data, Format and Operation subontologies. edamMap input is an EDAM ontology file and a file of tool descriptions. The latter should include tool name, short description, keywords and Pubmed identifier. Based on that the tool will automatically fetch relevant information and propose annotation terms for the curator to use when annotating tools and databases in bio.tools. edamMap has been used to annotate close to 2000 entries in bio.tools.

edamMap, and further documentation including usage instructions, are freely available:

<https://github.com/edamontology/edammap/>

J.2 OpenAPI-Importer

OpenAPI-Importer is a new utility, developed from scratch, for converting OpenAPI 2.0 documentation files into bio.tools format. Ontological annotations are not currently natively supported in OpenAPI 2.0, so support for EDAM annotations is provided by OpenAPI-Importer *via* an external JSON document. These annotations cover the service input parameters, for example, *Ensembl Gene ID* (http://edamontology.org/data_1033).

OpenAPI-importer has potential to provide useful support for curators in populating bio.tools, in a semi-automated way, with new entries for data service APIs. Much work remains to be done:

¹⁰⁰ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/100>

¹⁰¹ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com/issues/206>

- promoting use of openAPI specification by major database providers (currently very few use it)
- EDAM developments to provide coverage of service input parameters
- support in OpenAPI-Importer of the bio.tools API
- support OpenAPI 3.0 specification¹⁰², extending this to integrate EDAM ontology annotations directly, removing the need for a separate JSON files
- align with related emerging developments including smartAPI¹⁰³ and OpenRiskNet¹⁰⁴
- provide documentation, guidelines and other outreach materials

OpenAPI-Importer is freely available:

<https://github.com/bio-tools/OpenAPI-Importer/>

Appendix K: Licensing

The registry content is freely available to all under the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC BY 4.0), accordingly, members of the community may re-use the content for their own purposes and create their own interfaces tailored to their specific needs. EDAM and biotoolsSchema are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License (CC BY-SA 4.0), which afford the same freedoms, but require copies or adaptations of the work to be released under the same or similar licence as the original.

¹⁰² <https://github.com/OAI/OpenAPI-Specification/blob/OpenAPI.next/versions/3.0.md>

¹⁰³ <http://smart-api.info/website/>

¹⁰⁴ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/206759_en.html